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**SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE XXI CENTURY: CURRENT
ISSUES, DISCOVERIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS**

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NO	Author	Article Title	Page
1.	R.P. Ranjan Madugalle	SPIRITUALITY, ANCIENT TIMES AND PIONEER SKILL: PIONEER AWARENESS CREATION ON A FAMOUS RELIGIOUS SITE IN SRI LANKA	1-3
2.	Sankruti S.C.	CHITRAKUTA: HOLY SKETCH, HOLY PLACES AND TEMPLES	4-6
3.	J. Aslonov, N. Muhiddinova	LIE ALGEBRA OF SOLENOIDAL VECTOR FIELDS	7-9
4.	Gulzada Dauletmuratova, Ispandiyar Durshimbetov, Janabergen Khamidullaev, Soxib Mamatov, Asan Mambetnazarov	TYPES OF DISEASES IN TOMATOES AND TYPES OF MEASURES AGAINST THEM	10-12
5.	Zumrat Shapulatova, Umida Ruzikulova, Jonibek Kurbanov	PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF COLI-SALMONELLOSIS INFECTION IN CALVES	13-16
6.	Jayanti Kumar Sharma	FROM THE COMMON TO THE UNCOMMON: GUESSTIMATE THE ARCHEOLOGICAL PHOTOGRAPH OF THE KALI NADI – GANGES OROGRAPHY	17-20
7.	Nilufar Sapaeva	METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY	21-26
8.	Samariddin Ochilov	THE LEGAL DESCRIPTION OF REPLACING CRIMINAL PUNISHMENT WITH LESSER	27-32
9.	Bakhtiyorbek Usmonov	THEORETICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPT OF ADMINISTRATIVE JUSTICE	33-37
10.	Utkirjon Rajabov	CONSENSUS: SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION	38-41
11.	H. Russell Jones	THE DEBATE OF BELIEF: SELF AND THE GATHERED IN INDIAN FAITH	42-44
12.	R. Thomas	SHIELD OF ANTIBIOTIC FUNNEL ALTERNATE MOST BOLTED FROM GARCINIA KOLAAND COLA NITIDAFOR IN TOXICANT EQUITY	45-48
13.	Ja'farkhon Isakhonov	INNOVATIVE MECHANISMS OF SOCIAL SUPPORT OF YOUTH	49-53
14.	Abrorjon Kushmatov	LEGAL ISSUES OF APPLICATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY IN INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION	54-56
15.	Kamolbek Turdibekov, Ulugbek Mamadaliev	IMPROVING THE ACCURACY OF COMPENSATING DEVICES POWER CONTROL AT RAILWAY PARTITIONING POSTS	57-60
16.	Nawaz Salimullah	HOME GROWN SKIN SAFEGUARD AND PICTURE SAFEGUARD COMBINATION: A VICTIM ANALYSIS	61-63
17.	Z.Z. Rakhmonov	REFORMS TO REDUCE THE BUREAUCRATIC BARRIERS	64-67
18.	Sardor Amirkulov	SELF-GOVERNMENT OF CITIZENS – THE BASIS OF THE CONSTITUTIONAL SYSTEM	68-71

19.	Sherali Subkhonov	THE MAIN POINTS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN “ON INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION”	72-75
20.	J. Richard	IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE RESPECTS AND STRUCTURE OF ACTION OF B GLUCANS	76-78
21.	Shukhrat Bagirov	HISTORY OF FORMATION OF THE INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC SERVICE	79-83
22.	Mirzohid Zayniddin Ogli Qodirov	THE IMPORTANCE OF CITIES DURING THE KUSHAN EMPIRE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM	84-89
23.	S.R.Oltiboev, U.M.Ergashev	ASSESSMENT OF THE CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE MIDDLE EAR IN TYMPANOSCLEROSIS	90-94

SPIRITUALITY, ANCIENT TIMES AND PIONEER SKILL: PIONEER AWARENESS CREATION ON A FAMOUS RELIGIOUS SITE IN SRI LANKA

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ABSTRACT

The pursuit of this paper is coordinated to talk about the "compelling" part of pioneer information in the desultory developments of one of the famous journey locales, Sri Pada in Sri Lanka. What I investigate here is the manner by which distinctive legitimate talks arise about Sri Pada from the diverse pilgrim skill, Portuguese 1505-1687, Dutch 1687-1896 and British 1896-1948. As we currently know, legitimate talk on the 'colonized' was to a great extent created through the specialists of the provincial governments, military work force, Christian preachers, philologists and chairmen. In such manner, Sri Pada was not outstanding. I'm mindful that these types of information creation change with changes in the acts of expansionism. In this regard, I examine what gets recognized and checked by pilgrim approved information as 'Adam's Peak'.

KEYWORDS

Spirituality, expansionism, journey, Sri Lanka

INTRODUCTION

This paper talks about frontier information as found in the rambling developments of one of the mainstream journey locales, Sri Pada² in Sri Lanka. I investigate how extraordinary definitive talks arise about Sri Pada from the three diverse pioneer skill. As we presently know, definitive talk on the 'colonized' was to a great extent delivered through the specialists of the provincial governments, military faculty, Christian evangelists, philologists and directors. In such manner, Adam's Peak as it was called by the pioneer skill was not outstanding. These types of information creation change with changes in the acts

of expansionism. In this paper, I explore what gets distinguished and checked by frontier approved information as 'Adam's Peak' Such an examination is presently not new to humanities and the human sciences on the loose. Over the most recent twenty years, a huge group of information has been created to unload "a specific development of provincial information", under the sub-discipline the 'human studies of imperialism' (Pels: 1997). This line of examination has been an appealing way for some South Asian researchers, particularly, on India (Cohn: 1985, 1996; Guha: 1982, 1997; Dirks: 1992; Inden: 1990; Pandey: 1990; Chatterjee: 1993 and Chakrabarty: 2002) and on Sri Lanka (Spencer: 1990; Rogers: 1994; Scott: 1994; Jeganathan and Ismail: 1995; Roberts: 2001, 2003).

MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The development of the historical backdrop of Adam's Peak inside this structure is all the more extravagantly addressed in crafted by William Skeen, who was a functioning individual from the Colombo part of the Royal Asiatic Society and composed generally legitimate and the thorough record on 'Adam's Peak', named Adam's Peak: Legendary Traditional and Historic notification of The Samanala and Sri-Pada with A Descriptive Account of The Pilgrims' Route from Colombo to The ReligiousFoot-Print, distributed in Ceylon in 1870.²⁴ His content comprises of ten long graphic sections yet eight of them portray his excursion from the capital city of Colombo to Adam's Peak and the path back to Colombo

CONCLUSION

No place is the cycle of the creation of pioneer information more obvious than the frontier experience with the acts of "colorful" spirituality. 'Adam Peak' was made as a method of absorbing the outlandish individuals they were experiencing. Such absorption, as I have clarified, adjusted verifiably, with the progressions under the diverse provincial forces. It is very evident that the arrangement of Western information on Adam's Peak was itself

part of the bigger provincial creation of information on British Ceylon. As we see, the mid nineteenth century creation of information on Adam's Peak was to a great extent crafted by British military men; notwithstanding, by the center of the century it was generally delivered through the Christian pilgrim overseers who were considerably more coordinated as 'positivist ancient times specialist' under the umbrella of the Royal Asiatic Society.

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CHITRAKUTA: HOLY SKETCH, HOLY PLACES AND TEMPLES

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ABSTRACT

Chitrakuta, a position of Hindu journey for centuries on the waterway Mandākinī—spread over the two States of U.P. also, M.P.— has been fundamentally engaged by its relationship with Lord Rāma, who with his sibling Lakṣmaṇa and spouse Sītā, spent the primary phase of his fourteen-year banish in his wanderings through the wild. The kṣetra named after the Chitrakuta slope is a piece of the Vidhyān spike and the focal point of the heavenly zone. Other than caverns and springs, the two scene components thought about generally consecrated in Hindu custom—stream junctures and slopes—are available around there. Their importance to pioneers, without a doubt, gets from occasions described in the Ramayana of Vālmiki.

KEYWORDS : Ramayana, scene, blessed spots, journey, faithscape.

INTRODUCTION

Perusing the scene is an altruistic workmanship, unhindered to any field. The first importance of the word—image of a view—progressively changed to address the actual view Jackson 1984: 3-8 . The term scene has gone through a prominent change in its implication from appealing regular sketch to any humanly requested alteration of indigenous habitat. Sanskrit word references offer terms like bhū, bhūmi, sthala, kṣetra as interpretation of scene in the South Asian context. These terms hint land and outlined territory. Scene is more than actual setting and goes past simply working with human exercises. It tends to be noticed and deciphered as portrayal—sign and image—that encodes implications. 'It addresses social stories, imparting focal precepts of culture and lifestyles' Amita 2007: 4 . The imagery of holy scene makes a faithscape that envelops

hallowed spot, time, custom, and exemplifies both representative and substantial mind trying to understand humanity's character in the universe. The earth-soul is accepted to dwell in mountains, caverns, water-bodies and vegetation.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

At Chitrakuta, the pioneer's conviction that s/he is in reality at the focal point of the universe is fortified by encountering the dawn and dusk on the slopes. On Kāmadagiri slope, focal point of the kṣetra, s/he would see the mid year solstice dawn close to Bālājī and the colder time of year solstice dawn close to Hanumāndhārā. On the highest point of the slope at Sītārasoi close to Hanumāndhārā, s/he would see the mid year solstice dawn close to Vālmiki Āśrama slope and dusk above Kāmadagiri. Without a doubt, the slope culminations seem to brush the skies and achieve the sun's introduction to the world and passing. Kāmadagiri—which signifies "slope that awards wants"—is especially critical, in light of the fact that, it gets its force from being the area of Rāma, Sītā, and Lakṣmaṇa's cabins and is, subsequently, the hub mundi. The individual destinations in Chitrakuta are set apart by 'representative repetition', containing different layers of importance, consolidating topography, nearby practices, and epic folklore.

CONCLUSION

The climate of Chitrakuta in the past was loaded with thick and wonderful woods and beautiful slopes. Its foresty environmental factors had a decent otherworldly climate because of the presence of sages who were engaged in yogic practices or in compensation or in reciting the names of god. Yet, the consecrated spot is currently experiencing significant change. Deforestation and mushrooming development of structures and vehicles for the sake of advancement and foundation have obliterated a large part of the peaceful air. Sages are there generally occupied with common undertakings. This holy spot is situated in a dacoit pervaded area, police execute the dacoits, however, they spring up over and over. Because of their quality some holy places of the tīrtha are out of the scope of pioneers. The stream is experiencing contamination. Despite this, Chitrakūta is as yet a

quiet, calm, and tranquil spot where common excellence has, luckily, not yet been much spoiled by metropolitan development.

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LIE ALGEBRA OF SOLENOIDAL VECTOR FIELDS

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, solenoidal vector fields on three-dimensional Euclidean space are investigated. It is proved that Killing vector fields are solenoidal. It is also shown that the set of solenoidal vector fields is a Lie algebra with the Lie commutator.

KEYWORDS: Lie bracket, divergence, rotor, solenoidal vector fields, Killing vector fields

INTRODUCTION

Vector fields, the divergence of which is calculated in different physical applications, have very different physical meanings. However, everywhere the divergence of the vector field is directly related to flows through closed surfaces S .

The very concept of flow originally arose in hydrodynamics, when describing the motion of an incompressible fluid, the bulk density of which at all points in space is the same: $\rho = const$. Since the concept of hydrodynamic flow is closest to everyday experience, it makes sense to discuss it.

In addition to the gradient and divergence discussed above, applications often encounter another first-order differential operation called the rotor that maps vector fields to vector fields.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

It is known that the divergence and the curl are determined invariantly.

If a vector field $\vec{X}(x, y, z) = P(x, y, z)\vec{j} + Q(x, y, z)\vec{j} + R(x, y, z)\vec{k}$ is given in the space R^3 and the Cartesian coordinate system Oxyz is introduced, then they can be calculated by the following formulas

$$\operatorname{div}\vec{X}(M_0) = \frac{\partial P(M_0)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial Q(M_0)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial R(M_0)}{\partial z},$$

$$\operatorname{rot}\vec{X}(M_0) = (R_y - Q_z)\vec{i} + (P_z - R_x)\vec{j} + (Q_x - P_y)\vec{k}.$$

Now, using the properties of differential operations, we will prove several sentences that can be used in problems of the theory of vector analysis.

Definition 1. A scalar field depending only on the distance of a point to the origin is called spherical.

Proposition 1. If is a vector field of a spherical scalar field, then it is solenoidal in any region that does not contain the origin.

Divergence is a point characteristic of the distribution of sources and sinks. In the case of a solenoid field, there are no sources and sinks. An example of such a field is a magnetic field. This component of the electromagnetic field differs in that it is not generated by static elements such as a static electric charge. The absence of magnetic charges in nature from a mathematical point of view is a property of the solenoidality of the magnetic field.

Proposition 2. If X is a vector field of a spherical scalar field, then it is irrotational.

Let M be a smooth connected Riemannian manifold of dimension n, and a smooth vector field X is given on the manifold M.

Definition 2. A vector field X on M is called a Killing vector field if the one-parameter group of local transformations generated by the field X consists of isometries [6].

Example. In $M = R^3(x, y, z)$ – three-dimensional Euclidean space, there are six linearly independent Killing fields over the field of real numbers:

$$X_1 = \partial_1, X_2 = \partial_2, X_3 = \partial_3, X_4 = z\partial_2 - y\partial_3, X_5 = -z\partial_1 + x\partial_3, X_6 = y\partial_1 - x\partial_2.$$

The transformation groups generated by the vector fields X_1, X_2, X_3 are groups of parallel translations in the direction of the Ox, Oy, and Oz axes, respectively, and the last three are groups of rotations around the Ox, Oy, and Oz axes, respectively.

The Killing vector field has the following properties [6]:

1. The Lie bracket of two Killing fields gives the Killing field again.

2. A linear combination of Killing fields over the field of real numbers is also a Killing field. Therefore, the set of all Killing vector fields on the manifold M , forms a Lie algebra over the field of real numbers.

Proposition 3. The Killing vector field in three-dimensional Euclidean space is a solenoidal vector field.

Theorem. The Lie bracket of two solenoidal vector fields in three-dimensional Euclidean space is a solenoidal vector field.

Corollary 2. The set of solenoidal vector fields forms a Lie algebra with respect to the Lie bracket.

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TYPES OF DISEASES IN TOMATOES AND TYPES OF MEASURES AGAINST THEM

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the development of pathogenic microorganisms in tomato crops, the degree of damage and measures to combat them.

KEYWORDS: biotic factor, disease, pest, weed, microorganism, fungus, pathogen, microbiopreparation, fungicide.

INTRODUCTION

Along with providing food to the population, vegetable crops play a key role in the export potential of the Republic. Tomatoes are one of the most popular vegetable crops, rich in vitamins and carbohydrates and minerals.

Tomato is one of the most important and valuable vegetable crops, which plays an important role in human life, plays an important role in the diet.

Tomato fruit is extremely tasty and nutritious, it is eaten fresh, salted and marinated in addition to being eaten raw. It is an important raw material for the processing industry. [1] Tomatoes are grown in many countries around the world to meet the food needs of the world's population.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In our republic, tomatoes are grown on farms, in open fields, greenhouses and on the lands of the population. The specific climatic conditions of the republic make it difficult to cultivate. The hot and dry weather in the country, as well as low soil fertility, the proximity of groundwater, the high salinity of the soil have a negative impact on crop production.

In addition to the above abiotic factors, there are harmful biotic factors that to some extent adversely affect the growth and development of tomatoes, crop quality and quantity, leading to the loss of a certain part of the crop and even complete crop failure. Due to the fact that the tomato plant creates a favorable microclimate during the growing season, it is protected from harmful biotic factors: pests, diseases, weeds and the development of sparks.

During the growing season of tomatoes under the influence of various diseases a significant part of the crop is destroyed and the quality decreases sharply. As a result of failure to apply protective measures and other measures on a regular basis, diseases are common, especially in private backyards, and cause great harm. One of the main conditions for ensuring the cultivation of high and quality tomato crop is the protection of crops from disease. To do this, it is necessary to correctly identify the pathogen, its development, spread, information on how it is stored from one season to another, and on this basis to know the effective timing and methods of crop protection.

Among the pathogens of tomatoes, fungal species are very common. Among the types of fungal diseases in the Republic: Tomato phytophthora, fusarium wilt, tomato verticillium wilt, tomato black mold, tomato fruit rhizoctoniosis, tomato stem and fruit rot, tomato fruit rot, tomato fruit rot. [2]

CONTROL MEASURES. In order to protect tomatoes from diseases, first of all, it is important to properly organize the agro-technical measures. Before sowing the seeds should be treated with seed pesticides, taking into account the type, timing and method of sowing, irrigation and fertilizer application, complete decomposition in the application of organic fertilizers (manure

of various harmful biotic factors, spores of pathogens, pests). eggs and larvae are the main carriers for the spread of weed seeds).

CONCLUSION

In the biological control of them, we use the recommended types of fungicides - chemical fungicides - fungicides.

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PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF COLI-SALMONELLOSIS INFECTION IN CALVES

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ABSTRACT: Improving the prevention and treatment of coli-salmonellosis infection in calves . It focuses on the treatment of sick calves antimicrobial prep sensitivity of the bacteria aniqab farms, a disease of calves ngan selective use of antibiotics in the treatment results .

KEYWORDS: E.coli, colibacillosis, salmonellosis, calf, interflox, dithrim, sulfadimize, si profloxacin, limoxin, antibiotic, infection, immunity, vaccine, bacteria.

INTRODUCTION: In the economy of the republic, great importance is attached to the development of animal husbandry, which is the main branch of agriculture . However, mixed infections of farm animals, especially coli-salmonellosis mixed infections among young animals, are hampering the increase in the number of hooves in livestock and causing great economic damage to farms. Due to this, improving the diagnosis and prevention of coli-salmonellosis mixed infections remains one of the main and urgent problems in animal husbandry today.

THE MAIN FINDINGS: Samarkand region Pstdargom region " Jura " , "Hamza" farms calves packing salmonellosis disease for the treatment and prevention of the effects of prolonged Antibiotics rearrange the complex , to determine the sensitivity of some of the pathogenic antibiotics.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS: Microorganisms & D Management (chemical resistant to therapeutic devices, the possibility of selection rate) should remain, urgent problem for years to find a solution to the new and powerful drugs and bacterial infections resistant to their application in practice, the effective implementation of the composition of the purpose of scientific research and colibacteriosis we studied the susceptibility of salmonellosis pathogens to some antibacterial drugs.

RESEARCH RESULTS: "Jura" farm antibiotics limoksin 400 - 200, penstrep, supported siprofloksatsin. Sick calves for the treatment of their 8 three other groups skip the experience ib hopping. The first experimental group of calves in a muscle between 5 ml limoksin 200, the second group of muscles between 3 ml penstrep 400, and the third group siprofloksatsin 100 ml intravenous and oral pill 2 times 2. All calves in the experimental group the same day, once a mixed solution of 250ml saline solution askorbinka 4 ml, 4ml of vitamin B₁₂ to add intravenous injection.

Table 1

Results of treatment of sick calves with coli-salmonellosis mixed infection (farm "Jura")

Indicators	Groups		
	1experiment	2- experience	3- experiment
Age	Newborn	Newborn	Newborn
Calves (head)	8	8	8
Antibiotics	Limoxin 200	Penstrep 400	Ciprofloxacin n
Dose	5 ml m/o	3 ml m/o	100ml v / o 1 time per day, 0.5g 2 times per os
Additional	Saline solution 250ml + ascorbic acid 4 ml + vitamin 4ml v / into 1 time per day	Saline solution 250ml + ascorbic acid 4 ml + vitamin 4ml 1 time per day	Physiological erhythm 250ml + ascorbic acid 4 ml + vitamin B ₁₂ 4ml 1 time per day
Duration (days)	1-2	4-5	7-10
Heals (head)	8	6	7

Dead (head)	-	2	1
Efficiency (%)	100	75	87

Treatment with the drugs used in the 1st experimental group lasted 1-2 days, and all eight head calves recovered. Treatment with the drugs used in the 2nd experimental group lasted 4-5 days, six out of eight calves recovered, two died. Thus, the experiment showed that the effectiveness of the method we used in the treatment of sick calves in the first experimental group was 100%, in the second 75% and in the third 87% (Table 1).

In this case, for the treatment of five head sick calves of the 1st experimental group, we injected the drug interflox-100 subcutaneously in a dose of 1.5 ml once a day for two to three days. Calves in Experiment 3 were given 3-4 capsules of Rimfampicin orally at a time.

As a result of our research, treatment with the drugs used in the 1st experimental group lasted 2-3 days, during which time all five head of calves in the group recovered. Used in the second experimental group.

Treatment with drugs for 2-3 days, three to five calves healed, but one is dead. In the third experimental group, treatment with the drugs used lasted 5-7 days, and three out of five calves recovered, and two died.

Our experiments showed that the efficiency of the method we used in the treatment of sick calves in the first experimental group was 100%, in the second 80% and in the third 60% .

CONCLUSION: Vaccination of calves with a vaccine against coli-salmonellosis infection of calves is associated with changes in the immune background of the cow organism, which is exactly vaccinated to prevent the disease in calves. Therefore, it is used for prophylactic purposes by immunizing pregnant cows, and the emergence of colostral immunity gives effective results. This means that vaccination of pregnant cows 1.5-2 months before calving creates sufficient immunity in calves and is economically justified. In the treatment of sick calves it is advisable to study the susceptibility of bacteria to antimicrobial drugs and selective use. A treatment of calves farms at limoksin-200, interfloks-100 drugs can have a good effect.

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FROM THE COMMON TO THE UNCOMMON: GUESSTIMATE THE ARCHEOLOGICAL PHOTOGRAPH OF THE KALI NADI – GANGES OROGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The paper talks about the aftereffects of a surveillance overview completed in a space between the Kali Nadi and the Ganges waterways, which was focused on returning to recently detailed locales and furthermore for finding new destinations around there. Another point was to determine the degree to which archeological locales have made due in a seriously possessed zone and the effect of different normal and social variables following up on the destinations. The paper momentarily examines the ceramics and different antiques recuperated during the review just as about the spatial designing and circulation of archeological settlements around there.

KEYWORDS Archeological Survey, Upper Gangetic Doab, Ceramics, Artifacts, Kali Nadi

INTRODUCTION

Paleohistory has since a long time ago relied upon two essential procedures for producing information with respect to the past, which are unearthing and investigation. Both have various purposes, removal for acquiring top to bottom information with respect to the idea of a specific site, while investigation gives data on a bigger spatial level. It is progressively being acknowledged in paleohistory that intriguing information for understanding the idea of archeological destinations, identified with locales in a scene, can really be recuperated through review instead of removal.

MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS:

The territory that contains the subject of investigation in this paper is a lot of land situated between Kali Nadi and Ganga streams, which, thus, structure a piece of the Upper Ganga-Yamuna Doab. The region is delimited by facilitates $28^{\circ} 4'$ to $28^{\circ} 43'$ N and $77^{\circ} 18'$ to $78^{\circ} 28'$ E and falls inside the cutting edge regulatory locale of District Bulandshahr of Uttar Pradesh. The region has an all around created and an incorporated waste framework including both perpetual and occasional waterways just as little streams, brooks and lakes or Tals. The significant waterways that channel the region are the Ganga, Yamuna and Kali Nadi alongside some occasional streams like the Chhoiya or Nim Nadi. The territory shows a uniform geology with a delicate slope from north-west to south-east and has rich and ripe soils, making it perhaps the most significant and agronomically progressed locale of Uttar Pradesh.

METHODS

The overview program basically centered around returning to every one of the recently detailed archeological destinations around there and recording them in a more intensive way just as to investigate the remainder of the scene for new locales to be added to the archeological guide of the space. The point was to find locales inside the scene just as to comprehend their designing and circulation. In the wake of making every one of the essential arrangements, it was chosen to do a regular "town to town" overview to reconsider and concentrate every one of the recently announced locales just as to investigate the remainder of the space for new destinations. The region was to a great extent navigated by walking or utilizing a bullock-truck, as a large portion of the towns in the review territory are associated exclusively by slender sloppy tracks and a few destinations were exceptionally hard to approach because of the profoundly harmed nature of the streets. To find archeological destinations in the towns, the nearby occupants helped in recognizing and looking over the locales.

CONCLUSION

The information produced during the current overview gives an essential structure to acquire a knowledge into the scene and the arrangement of archeological settlements across it just as to comprehend the different common and social cycles that have had an impact in the designing of these settlements before and keep on doing as such in the present. The previous studies had principally recorded the ceramics found at different destinations. While this has been significant in giving a thought of the order of the locales, less significance was given to the position of destinations in the scene. The current study has had the option to plan the common locales all the more precisely with the assistance of Global Positioning System arranges, just as comparable to the closest water sources to every one of the destinations. The current study has likewise had the option to get a gauge of the site sizes, just as recuperate information for locales not saw before.

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METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT: This article provides suggestions on how to assess the level of sustainable development of the region's economy and, in particular, on the methods of sustainable development of Khorezm region.

KEYWORDS: Sustainability, economic development, GRP(gross regional product) economic indicators, environmental indicators, social indicators, industry, agriculture, investment, infrastructure

INTRODUCTION

An important issue is to study the stable and balanced level of economic development of the region. Herein, we assess the stability of the region by the state of a number of indicators. In these criteria of gross regional product (GRP), its per capita volume, the volume of products created in industries and sectors, the volume of exports, their growth trends are studied.

Among the aforementioned indicators, the volume of GRP and its real growth rate are of particular importance in assessing sustainability. Because this indicator is a general representation of economic and social processes, it is a general reflection of the production potential of the region as well. Including the economic potential of the region and its differences from other regions the real are assessed by the real level of GRP. In addition, when the lifestyle of the population is studied, the increase in GRP per capita is estimated.

GRP generated in Khorezm region is average compared to other regions of the country. GRP variation trends in 2010-2020 have been uneven and have declined in recent years. In other words, it decreased from 107.1% in 2010 to 102.3% in 2020. The average growth rate of GRP created in the region during the study period was 106.6%. This figure is equal to the average in

the regions of the country. Nevertheless, we pay special attention to assessing its level of sustainability.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Appropriate methods should be investigated to assess the sustainability of GRP created in Khorezm region in relation to the regions of the country. There are a number of methodological approaches to the study of regional economic stability. In particular, most approaches study sustainability in terms of economic, social, and environmental issues. However, when evaluating them, the indicators are initially normalized. The result is summarized, then compared and the relative situation is assessed.

The methodological approach studied by a group of authors developed assessment methods based on the generalization of economic, social and environmental criteria for the sustainability of the region.

S.A. Egorychev's (С.А.Егорычев) research also covered economic, social, and environmental indicators. In this approach, the author studies three relevant aspects in the determination of overall stability on the basis of an integral method as well. The same approach was used in L.A. Fedorova's (Л.А.Федорова) research. That is, in the evaluation process, economic, environmental, and social indicators were calculated

O.Khokhlova and M.Budajanaeva (О.Хохлова и М.Будажанаева) used an integral method to assess the sustainable development of the region. However, similar to the approaches above, they have taken into account three aspects: economic, social and environmental issues.

To determine the economic sustainability of the region based on the methods developed by the researchers above, we will carry out the following series of steps. First of all, it is expedient to normalize the indicators. To do this, we need to study the differences between the relevant indicators relative to the highest and lowest values in the region. That is, we offer the following normalization method:

$$norm = \frac{Real - Min}{Max - Min} \quad (1)$$

In this case: Norm - the normalized level of the relevant criterion; Real - the amount of real indicators for the region; Max - the maximum amount of indicators in the regions; Min - the minimum amount of indicators in the regions.

When we evaluate the criteria obtained on the basis of the above equation on the basis of several indicators, we estimate the arithmetic mean. We obtain the ratio of the sum of the corresponding criteria to their number. That is, to calculate the stability index, we propose the following equation:

$$NI = (Norm_1 + Norm_2 + Norm_3 + \dots + Norm_m) * \frac{1}{m} \quad (2)$$

Where: NI is the stability index of the region; m - is the number of indicators selected and evaluated to determine stability.

This represents the level of sustainability of the development of the respective region. Based on this approach, we calculate the economic stability of the regions of the republic through a single criterion - real change in GRP.

First, using this method, we determine the economic stability of Khorezm region in relation to the regions of the republic. Herein, we take into account the real growth rates of GRP in the regions. We assess the conditions in years 2010-2020 in our study. The results show that Khorezm region has average values among the regions of the republic. In particular, the analysis of indicators in Khorezm region was equal to the average values in the regions of the republic, that is (0.5).

The above trend indicates the availability of resources and opportunities to increase the scale of production of the economy in Khorezm region. That is, this situation indicates the presence of empty production factors in the economy. In addition, the share of agriculture in GRP is high, it can also be justified by the fact that it is half. This industry is a link that creates raw materials for industry. The agricultural sector in the country is mainly characterized by extensive development. This is because manual labor is high in the agricultural sector and is a labor-intensive sector. Its high volume in the GRP of Khorezm region indicates the presence of idle factors of production in the region.

Therefore, due to the high employment of the labor force in agriculture in Khorezm region at the present time, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of industry. It is necessary to develop small business in the industrial sector. As a result, there will be an opportunity to process agricultural raw materials. On the other hand, overall productivity will increase as a result of the shift of agricultural labor to industry.

In particular, labor productivity by industry is relatively high in industry. Even in the services sector, labor productivity is higher than in agriculture. This requires an assessment of the network structure of GRP in increasing the income of the population in Khorezm region.

That is, as mentioned above, we will conduct relevant research on the structure of the level of sectors and on this basis the structural aspects of GRP.

The main part of GRP created in Khorezm region belongs to agriculture. In particular, the share of industries in value added is 50.7% in agriculture, 16.5% in industry and 32.8% in services.

Therefore, the regional economy is in line with the type of agro-industrial development. Special attention should be paid to industrialization in order to ensure the further sustainable development of the economy. Moreover, the availability of sufficient reserves for food and light industry in this sector is due to the high share of agriculture.

At the same time, special attention should be paid to the relatively young machinery industry in the region. That is, it is necessary to increase production and exports in accordance with current and future demand, taking into account the markets of neighboring countries.

One of the main factors in the process of industrialization of the economy is investment. Especially, its norm is an important indicator. In particular, during the period of high growth and industrialization in the economies of countries such as South Korea, China and Japan, the investment rate averaged 30%. Thus, for the industrialization of Khorezm region, first of all, it is necessary to study the level of this factor.

The investment rate in Khorezm region, to put it another way, the share of investments in GRP for 2010-2020 was 23.3%. However, this figure has fluctuated unevenly over the research period and has been increasing in recent years.

It should be noted that with the growth of this indicator, the share of industry in GRP is also changing in a mutual agreement. In particular, in the years when its share was between 26-30 percent, the share of industry also reached its highest values. This means that the economy of Khorezm region currently requires an investment rate of 30% and above for the industrialization and modernization of the economy. To achieve this level, special attention should be paid to the expansion of entrepreneurial activity in Khorezm. Along with this, given that Khorezm is geographically bordered by neighboring countries, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of infrastructure. Infrastructure development directly provides capital growth. In particular, as a result of the launch of railway infrastructure in the United States, the market for goods and services has grown sharply.

Along with the scale of investment, it is equally important to ensure the effective use of this opportunity. The indicator that represents the aspects of efficiency and is used to assess

the impact of its share on the economy is the capital capacity of economic development, the ICOR (Incremental Capital Output Ratio). In Khorezm region, this figure averaged 4.2 units during the study period.

In recent years, however, this figure has been growing. This process indicates that GRP is capital-intensive, that is, it indicates the efficiency of using the capital factor is declining. In particular, the experience of a number of foreign countries shows that the ICOR coefficient is effective when it is in the range of 3-3.5.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, special attention should be paid to attracting foreign investment to increase the efficiency of capital use in the regional economy and accelerate the process of industrialization. This is because the change in the share of foreign investment in total investment was positively correlated with efficiency when studying the trend in the regional economy. Along with this, special attention should be paid to the skills of the workforce in the region. Herein, attention should be paid to the formation of innovative infrastructure for the development of higher education and industrial integration.

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THE LEGAL DESCRIPTION OF REPLACING CRIMINAL PUNISHMENT WITH LESSER

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ABSTRACT: In this scientific article is intended to the role of the penalty as a type of punishment for the release of the sentence, fundamentals of lighter changes, the practice of applying scientific and theoretical views and law, the relevance of the conditions and categories of replacement of punishment, conditions, change of punishment with lighter, the situation with a lighter in punishment and the emergence of changes in the convict, revisiting the terms of the punishment with lightly replacement, the conditions for serving the next penalty, which are exalted in the penalty, described in the improvement of legislative and legal practice.

KEYWORDS: the restriction of the sentence, court, sentence, punishment, freedom, release from punishments, correctional activities.

INTRODUCTION

The court shall consider the nature of the nature and social danger of the crime, the damage, the cause of the damage, the cause of the damage, the personality and punishment for the crime, the nature of the damage, the personality, and the punishment.

Naturally, law enforcement officers should not stand as a decrease in the number of sentences in imprisonment – the purpose of the Institute of Punishment. Nevertheless, this second-level impact is notable to great importance, early use of certain types of exemption sometimes leads to unnecessary consequences. [10, pg. 7].

During the convict, he fulfills a number of commitments and changes in his social behavior. The treatment of the convict to the obligations to serve the sentence and the state of social conduct should also increase the need to review the current penalties appointed relative to him. The growth of criminals imprisonment is an ideal opportunity to draw attention to the prison of the prison, but it is not an easy task [6, pg. 7].

In case of certain existing circumstances, the punishment can be changed in a more lighter form, served as a basis for replacement of their total [9, ctp. 270]. The Replacement of punishment is one of the criminal legal measures aimed at achieving the goal of a criminal penalty. The ultimate goal of the punishment The ultimate goal is to morally, when such a goal is achieved, the continued penalties is important.

The punishment should be so that it should respond in accordance with the crime of the convict and be properly applied to social behavior. Although the penalty is worthy of a specific type of punishment for the crime, the punishment is made of a penalty, which must be exempted from incumbent, or another dimensional and other punishment. The punishment or other legal influence applied to a person accused in the commission of a crime is the principle of righteousness of the criminal law.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The court shall provide for persons convicted of Article 74 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1], which can replace the sentence with a lighter part of the sentence.

It is estimated that a person's limitations can only restrict freedom where the freedom is to be dangerously [7, pg. 57]. In replacement of punishment with a lighter, the convict is a criteria for assessing the requirements set for the appropriate procedure for relevant penalty.

The theory of the convicted moral controls studies the crime as a result of social diseases and considers rehabilitation target to be correction in the convict rehabilitation centers. The penalties aimed at moral correction must be adapted to a criminal not a crime [5, pg. 20].

It is also one of the main conditions that the criminal law has a separate part of the concrete penalty. In replacement of punishment, convict may be used after the following parts of the sentence established for certain types of sentences:

- a) at least one-fourths of the sentence imposed on a court not to be a large or less disturbed crime;
- b) for a crime of serious crime, also for the intentional crime, if he was sentenced to imprisonment for a felatorium before, at least one-third of the punishment imposed on the court;

c) for a very serious crime, it is also used pre-suspected or lighter in a penalty and for a new crime that has intentionally committed intentionally during the punitive part of the punishment at least half of the sentence imposed.

In order to replace the punishment with a lighter, it is necessary to fulfill a number of obligations imposed on the sentence. So, two categories conditions are interpreted by a person with a lighter replacement requires fulfillment of two categories:

the first category, fulfillment of requirements of procedure set for penalty types and honest treatment of labor;

the second category, action of certain part of the deadline for penalty types.

It is noted that modern methods of legal education are depend on the existing socio-political and legal situation in the society, as well as the legal worldviews and perfection of the population [3, pg. 20]. In particular, improving the legal education of prisoners is also a tool that helps to ensure that they may simply exchange their sentences. Therefore, the conditions and awareness of the sentences from the possibilities to replace the sentences and the conditions of the possibility that it is aware of the need to develop their legal education.

The Court of Justice, including the presence of a state of conviction for previous crimes, the assigned penalty is a short time in a particular penalties that it does not plead guilty to convicted guilt and etc have no right to release or re-submit a sentence or punishment with a sentence of the sentence [2].

In order to replace the punishment, the person should be recognized as the main criterion that his conduct, the fact that he actually went to the corruption path. The main purpose of the punishment involves the formation of positive changes in the conduct of the convict. Therefore, in order to investigate and replace the convicts with a lighter, it is important to focus on the study and assessment.

It is also necessary to ignore the liability for the crime committed. Of course, the person must answer by serving his sentence for the crime. Therefore, in replace the sentence, the person shall continue to serve the relatively lightly kind of penalty without being released from the appointed first penalty. Lighter replacement is an important role in encouraging the positive behavior of the convict.

Persons who have been replaced by lighter punishment may be subjected to early sentences after the provisions established by the specified part of the lighter punishment. During serving a lighter severe penalty, the prisoner complies with the established procedures

for the current penalty, while the current part of the current penalty may be released in a pre-appointed sentence.

The court must conclude that the purpose of the punishment can be achieved by using a different type of punishment in time when solving the unregistered part of the sentence with lightly. The next lighter type penalty is to be compatible with the actual behavior of the convict, it plays an important role in not light or difficult. It does not have a legal design of the subsequent conduct of the lighter severe penalty, and only when it is intentionally committing a delibgeon.

When the penalties appointed relative to the convict, the service of exchanged lighter penalties (fine from imprisonment, correctional affairs of freedom, correctional affair). The probation is an alternative to imprisonment. Credited as a criminal criminal in prison is lending to the other direction [8, pg. 27]. The regime of prutism is also valid in accordance with the exchange of lighter types. To date, the views of the implementation of the primary punishment will be replaced by a slight punishment to be replaced by a slight punishment forms and lifting a lighter type penalty. It should be noted that the person is honest for the work imposed during the penalty, but is not replaced by the penalty, which is prepared for it, and the imposed prisoner has not yet actually passed the part of the law. In this case, the convict is important that the convict compliance with the procedures established for its imposed part of the sentences relative to him and honestly reacted to work for its assigned penalties.

The priority is to follow the procedure for penalty and honestly imposed on the sentence imposed on the convict to replace the sentence with a lighter exchange. The institute of punishment is an important role in raising the institute as an incentive tool in the upbringing and mansulture of convictions. Researchers – in view of the participation of prisoners in the course of education, the research recognized that if the convict is actively involved in this process, it has been appropriate to fill in it with the norm on respect of him in this process. [4, pg. 22].

CONCLUSION

Given the procedure for serving the criminal law and the procedure for serving the appointed sentence to it, it is proposed to replace the specified number of penalties, which can replace the specified parties, without serving their sentences.

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THEORETICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPT OF ADMINISTRATIVE JUSTICE

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ABSTRACT: This article is devoted to the theoretical foundations of the concept of administrative justice. This article describes in detail the types of the concept of administrative justice studied by scholars and its practical and theoretical foundations. Not only the theoretical foundations of the concept of administrative justice, but also the practical foundations are illustrated using examples.

KEYWORDS: conception, administrative justice, division of powers, foreign scientists, disputes, public law.

INTRODUCTION

In the legislation of each state there are legislative, executive and judicial bodies, these bodies, in turn, reflect the print of the division of powers and have their own incomparable place in the construction and formation of the state. Among these, the judicial body plays a special role. Because the disputes that have arisen will be considered and resolved through these courts. In this regard, the administrative system of Justice, aimed at resolving mass legal disputes, occupies a special place.

Directly referring to the concept of administrative Justice, many foreign scientists expressed their opinion on this. In particular, " administrative Justice - this means direct control over the subjects of Public Law."

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

J. Ne'matov said that administrative Justice would be aimed at abolishing a certain legal force or finding it invalid.

Sterilov said that administrative Justice is a system of protection by the court in the event of violation of the rights of citizens in public administration.

K.Belsky noted that administrative Justice is considered a processual relationship connected with the separate procedure for the consideration in court of complaints of citizens about the illegal actions of officials (state bodies), as well as the protection of the rights of a citizen by the abolition of the act of illegal management.

In addition,"administrative Justice is a system of special judicial review and settlement of administrative and legal disputes arising from the relations of Public Administration between state bodies and officials, citizens and legal entities".

According to Adler, administrative Justice is a system that ensures that decisions made by administrative bodies are taken correctly and serves to ensure justice.

In our opinion, administrative Justice is the solution of administrative and judicial disputes arising from the relations of Public Administration between state bodies and officials, citizens and legal entities in the administrative and judicial order.

Proceeding from the above definitions, it should be noted that there is no single definition of the concept of Administrative Justice. But it is possible to observe that there are general aspects of these definitions. In particular, the fact that it is a mechanism for resolving administrative disputes is a common feature.

The administrative and legal nature of disputes arising from these administrative-legal relations is determined by the following::

- these types of disputes arise in connection with the implementation of state management functions of state bodies;
- administrative disputes arise as a result of the adoption of legal and regulatory decisions within the framework of administrative-legal relations and the discontent of the second party with respect to them.

Hence, from the above points of view, it is possible to give a general description of administrative and legal disputes as follows::

- administrative-legal dispute is a dispute over the rights and obligations of the subjects of administrative law;
- administrative-legal dispute is an expression of discontent of one of the subjects of administrative-legal relations on the fact of accepting the act of illegal management;
- administrative-legal disputes arise in connection with the implementation of managerial functions by the executive body. So, one of the subjects of the
- administrative dispute is of course the state body or the person of the official.

Proceeding from these above rules, we can say that the disputes that make up the subject of administrative justice can be divided into two types:

First, administrative and legal disputes arising as a result of the commission of actions (inaction) by state bodies and officials that violate the rights and freedoms of citizens;

Secondly, disputes arising as a result of decisions made by state bodies and officials that violate the rights and freedoms of citizens.

As we can see, the disputable administrative and legal relations that make up the subject of administrative Justice arise between state administrative bodies, officials and citizens. Also, these disputes arise as a result of the implementation of decisions or actions within the framework of the main tasks and functions enshrined in the main narcotic-legal acts regulating the activities of the state governing bodies.

Another issue on the scientific and theoretical foundations of the concept of administrative justice is the question of whether this concept of administrative justice is an introduction to the subject of administrative law or not. Scientific sources describe a number of issues about this. Proceeding from the need to carry out reforms in administrative law, it should be noted that today, as a subject of Administrative Law, Administrative Justice relations should also be introduced. This can be based on:

First, the subject of administrative law is the relationship to management, that is, the activities of the executive bodies. One of the main prints of the organization and

functioning of the executive power is the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens, ensuring their superiority. Article 2 of the Common Law (Constitution) of our state defines the responsibility of state bodies and officials before society and citizens. One of the main tasks of the Administrative Court is also the implementation of judicial control over the activities of executive bodies.

Secondly, citizens are considered one of the main subjects of administrative law, that is, when it comes to the organization and functioning of executive power, it has a specific legal status. Citizens have the right to participate in the process of Public Administration; each person is guaranteed by the state the right to apply to the courts for illegal actions of state bodies and officials, as well as administrative acts. Of course, therefore, judicial control over the activities of state bodies is of great importance.

Thirdly, one of the important institutions of administrative law is the civil service. In the same way, servants of Public Administration bodies, officials can undermine the rights and interests of citizens by their actions and decisions during the implementation of the powers assigned to them.

Fourthly, one of the main legal forms of Public Administration is the adoption of management acts. Administrative justice also presupposes control over the legality of public administration acts.

Fifth, the state, through its bodies and officials, takes administrative measures in relation to individuals and legal entities. Administrative Justice serves as the only judicial protection in the case of improper application of administrative offenses by state bodies and officials.

Sixth, administrative Justice is also inextricably linked with the institution, as is the administrative process of administrative law.

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CONSENSUS: SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION

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ABSTRACT: The term consensus is used as an international term to refer to a decision made by a parliament or council in the conclusion of an international treaty, unless there is a formal objection, in the decision-making process by consensus of the parties. [1] It is also recognized as a consensus method and is used in international conferences and councils held within the UN.

KEYWORDS: consensus, people's consent, community, education, social contract, human factor.

INTRODUCTION

The term also refers to agreement, solidarity, partnership, coherence, and is used when two or more people have similar interests, allowing them to understand each other or build relationships. By general definition, the attitude in any sphere of human activity is the consensus of the majority of the socially significant majority of any community in relation to society to the most important aspects of the social order established in it.

We can show that the consensus method is formed at the cultural level on the principle of "people's consent", which is the basis of all reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan and is defined as a priority task of state organizations. Consensus also plays an important role in the national mentality and worldview of our people. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis of December 29, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. At the heart of these views of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the process of cooperation and collaboration, which is one of the most important qualities of our people and a manifestation of the consensus studied in the field of research.

In the socio-economic policy of Uzbekistan, the pursuit of unrealistic figures, the unrealistic way of presenting unrealistic fantasies as a reality, has been critically reconsidered.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Problems that have accumulated over the years have been identified and addressed on a door-to-door basis, but today problems are being studied in a “neighborhood” way and solved on the basis of a new system.

The aim of the new system is to ensure justice and transparency by taking into account the views of the people in the implementation of any reforms in the country, the submission of its draft for public discussion in the adoption of any regulations.

Consensus and consensus play a key role in resolving issues and making decisions by consensus, and by bringing this method to the level of culture, we are able to solve the current problems in our society today.

Consensus has been extensively studied by Western scholars, philosophers and sociologists. In particular, the English educator and philosopher John Locke examined the cognitive (and partly psychological) factors of consensus education in the context of the idea of social contract, which is reflected in the motto "Thoughts govern the world". Advocating that education is the basis of this treaty, "both evil and goodness in man, both harmful and harmful, are the fruit of education," he stressed.

The German philosopher G.W.Hegel was the first to advance the question of how to ensure "mutual recognition" by the people, for whom consensus is the most general condition of the possibility of society. In order for a consensus to emerge, he put forward the idea of resolving conflicts. To do this, he analyzed the nature of the contradictions and stressed that in the process of their development, denial should be resolved not only as a denial, but also as a denial. The first denial is the discovery of contradictions, and the second is their resolution. [3]

Later, as a result of these studies, sociologists developed another principle of consensus, the principle of "general agreement". This was the basis of the "positive sociology" of the French philosopher and sociologist O.Conte, who had to discover the laws of harmony between different parts of society on the basis of generally accepted values of all the constituent elements of society. Achieving universal consensus, that is, the unity of values and

norms, is seen as the guiding principle of all positivist sociology. (Incorporated into the works of E. Durkheim, W. Pareto, T. Parsons).

A similar approach to understanding consensus Le Bon (the law of spiritual unity), G. Tarde (the law of imitation of human behavior) and E. Durkheim are characterized by the notion that consensus is the organic property of rational, "normal" ("healthy") social life.

In contrast, Weber did not view consensus as an attribute of "normal" societies, but as an integral feature of any human society, it is characterized by tension, conflict of interest, and multifaceted tendencies. The consensus is that in Weber's view, the probability that exists objectively is ahead of him. Agreements ("social contract" and others), participants in this or that form of human relations, consider each other's expectations to be important for their actions, which they must adapt to in one way or another.

Behaviors based on "consent" are different from actions based on "interpretation" of the consensus. The consensus, according to Weber, is that there is a certain minimum consistency in reciprocity and movement, and that it must be committed before the "contract."

In America, consensus problems have spread to the micro level of small groups (Cooley, L. Wirth, and others) and have been analyzed in terms of "symbolic interactions" (J.G. Mead). E. Shiels considers consensus in the context of the relationship between the center and social systems, linking consensus with respect for the center of the system, which includes personality, roles, institutions, beliefs and norms. In this case, consensus can be reached between the "branches of the social system" as a "state of effective solidarity" in matters of general order (distribution of power, income, prestige) (ie, in the absence of agreement) on personal matters. This general consensus will continue to escalate to the point where disagreements of a certain order will destroy the "influential element" of unity. He concludes that the "relatively rigid" systems of classes and ethnic groups are internally opposed to achieving a full consensus that encompasses society as a whole.

CONCLUSION

In short, the achievement of unity of values and norms, the consent of the people, and the fact that this agreement serves the public interest in reaching agreement in different situations must form the basis of a culture of consensus.

The education of members of society plays an important role in raising the consensus to the level of culture. This is because in resolving various conflicts, the main goal should be the "human factor" and the compromise should serve the good, not the victory of one party over the other or the interests of one group of the community.

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THE DEBATE OF BELIEF: SELF AND THE GATHERED IN INDIAN FAITH

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ABSTRACT

The current paper means to inspect the marvels of custom and culture with uncommon accentuation on two related perspectives: the ontological/otherworldly direction that any practice has, and the social and metro esteems the custom proposals to the general public. Appropriately, the essential construction of the current investigation follows a three-crease way: hypothetical comprehension of custom and its arguments; recovering this idea in the Indian social practice and discovering its ontological moorings; philosophical supplication that the social custom of India is established in the ideas of Dharma, ṛta and yajña.

KEYWORD

Logic, culture, society, metaphysics, position framework.

INTRODUCTION

As the practice assumed a basic part in the antiquated society, there had been a consistent undertaking to communicate and pass on the sent convictions and customs in a particular structure and articulation to other people. This cycle is portrayed by a pressure and the need to make it significant because of the predominant conditions. In a word, custom is a way or example of reasoning, doing or making a move which is acquired from the past. The beginning of the word custom can be followed back to the Latin thing traditio , got from the action word tradere . The word traditio relates near the Greek word paradosis, which likewise has a similar importance. In old occasions, Latin and Greek scholars utilized traditio and paradosis, in the feeling of lessons safeguarded and gave over by the Church

as "the Catholic confidence". Hence, 'communicating' and 'giving over' had been the key significance of the underlying Greek word *Paradosis* and Latin *tradere*. There can be no practice without institution. The institution of a practice includes certain consistencies of direct. Custom can nor be received nor does it spread, however, it is just given over

MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The idea of arrangement is consistently a reference to the molding or shaping of human existence. In certain actions, each human subject is shaped verifiably and unequivocally by either developmental custom or by the combination of them. Developmental custom alludes to the structure mandates that have been given over from one age to another. Primary developmental custom alludes to the widespread mandates and legitimacy. It is not, at this point bound solely to the particularities of past or present socio-recorded circumstances. Developmental customs have been the main stores of structure rules for human existence and society. Their coherence has been upheld and supported by the strict or humanistic conviction frameworks where they are established. Appropriately, developmental practices are supported through letters, images, inventive legends, rituals and customs which delivered basic and incredible into the ever-enduring structure orders. As it were, we can say that the developmental practices discover their solidarity in images, stories, ceremonies, and compositions that are profoundly significant and sustain living confidence, expectation and consonance in the arrangement secret.

CONCLUSION

We have been contending that the center of Indian custom and its philosophical vision is established in the transcendentalism of the experience of *Dharma*, *yajña*, and *ṛta*, which we might want to call as the social metaphysics of India that had been concluded from its fanciful reasoning. From this enticing power of involvement, Indian way of thinking could create an exceptional domain of solidarity that ties the aware as well as the insentient creatures. Consequently, the Indian practice by its nonexclusive nature couldn't underline an idea of division as communicated in the western mysticism, however, have featured the

idea of solidarity. Appropriately, in its comprehension of being Indian way of thinking is drastically not the same as the western idea of being. In the western idea of being, what we see is the important accentuation on the detachment ensured by the need of resistance; in its comprehension of being, the idea of yajña is transcendent in Indian idea, which requires the chance of meeting the other as a vital piece of oneself. There is a particular Indian metaphysics whose comprehension of being compares to a particular perspective. The essence of this particular perspective is communicated by various ideas of time.

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SHIELD OF ANTIBIOTIC FUNNEL ALTERNATE MOST BOLTED FROM GARCINIA KOLAAND COLA NITIDAFOR IN TOXICANT EQUITY

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ABSTRACT

Targets: Plant antibiotic parasites are novel repository of bioactive mixtures. The point of this study was to investigate antibiotic parasites from *Garcinia kola* and *Cola nitida* for cancer prevention agent auxiliary metabolites Methods: Six contagious endophytes, Gn1-3 and Cn1-3 were disengaged from the restorative plants *G. kola* and *C. nitida* separately. The unadulterated endophytes were aged, their rough optional most bolted removed and evaluated for cancer prevention agent equity utilizing 1, 1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl searching exercises and lessening power test. The bioactive standards were identified by dereplication utilizing High Performance Liquid Chromatography-Diode Array Detector investigation

KEYWORDS: *garcinia kola* and *cola*, antibiotic, anticipation and improvement

INTRODUCTION

oxidative stress, which emerges from the presence of responsive oxygen species has been set up to be associated with the improvement of different wellbeing problems . Problems

connected to extreme age of RESPONSIVE OXYGEN SPECIES in the human body incorporate malignant growth, irritation, Alzheimer's illness, dementia, cardiovascular infections and atherresponsive oxygen species cleresponsive oxygen species . The utilization of products of the soil known to have cell reinforcement movement has demonstrated helpful in avoidance and improvement of a portion of these sickness states. As of late, colossal exploration endeavors have been coordinated towards the improvement of restorative cancer prevention agent compounds from these therapeutic plants. One of the final products of the commercialization of effective cell reinforcement compounds got from plant source might be huge scope collecting and likely annihilation of such plants, which thus could prompt environment unevenness and natural disturbance . This highlights the need to investigate elective and ecofriendly business wellsprings of recognized therapeutic mixtures

MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Leaf tests of *Cola nitida* (PCG/473/A/051) and *Garcinia kola* (PCG/473/A/052) were gathered from develop sound plants from Nsukka, in Enugu State situated in South-Eastern piece of Nigeria. They were recognized by Mrs. Emezie Anthonia of the Department of Pharmacognosy and Traditional Medicine, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. Plant materials were brought to the research center in sterile packs and prepared inside a couple of hours after assortment. Tests were likewise saved at the herbarium of the Department of Pharmacognosy and Traditional Medicine, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria.

RESULTS AND CONVERSATION

Revolutionary searching action is extremely pivotal to the endurance of living creatures, since their quality outcomes in a few harms to the body frameworks. As prior said, utilization of cell reinforcements, either as natural products or vegetables is valuable for anticipation and improvement of some ailments. Strangely, separates from parasitic disengages of *G. Kola* and *C. nitida* demonstrated a checked revolutionary rummaging action. Phenolic compounds have cell reinforcement properties¹⁵. The most noteworthy rummaging movement was displayed by Cn_3 and it is intriguing to see that every one of the mixtures recognized in Cn_3 are phenolic compounds. The diminishing limits of the concentrates of Cn_3 and Gc_3 could too be ascribed to the chief mixtures recognized in the concentrates by HPLC examination. P-hydroxybenzoic responsive oxygen speciesive, protocatechuic responsive oxygen speciesive, and indole-3-acidic responsive oxygen speciesive have all been accounted for to have cell reinforcement impacts .

CONCLUSION

All in all, the outcomes from these in vitro experiments showed that dynamic mixtures in the antibiotic contagious concentrates from *C. nitida* and *G. kola* have critical cell reinforcement exercises. The optional most bolted present in these antibiotic organisms have potential for drug and agrochemical applications. Notwithstanding, enormous scope reaping of these plants could untowardly influence environmental change. On the other hand, antibiotic parasites from these plant leaves could fill in as an eco cordial reasonable wellspring of characteristic cancer prevention agents for drug enterprises. Besides, there

might be need to direct more examination on these parasitic concentrates. These would include intensifies cleaning and portrayal, just as in vivo research methods.

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INNOVATIVE MECHANISMS OF SOCIAL SUPPORT OF YOUTH

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ABSTRACT: The formation of social activity of young people and its study create the conditions for creating ideas about the level of the socio-political state of society. The article covers such aspects as: the importance of disclosing the basic concepts of the state youth policy, the need to protect from the influence of various alien ideologies in the period of globalization; substantiated and voiced in scientific circles conclusions and recommendations aimed at improving the spiritual growth of young people, the continuous development of their social and civic responsibility, as well as increasing the effectiveness of youth organizations.

KEYWORDS: Young People, Globalization, Culture, Social Activity, Socio-political Knowledge, Globalization, Youth Organizations

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the development of civil society, the social interests of the youth, who are the main level of society, and ensuring their rights and freedoms are an important task. Important promising measures are being taken to ensure the effectiveness of the vital activities of the youth in the context of national development, which are a key principle of human interests and well-being. Ideas for development in society, the effectiveness of the priorities of civil society will depend on the level of well-being of the youth.

The youth belong to the internationally recognized category of population. The social status of the youth has also been determined in foreign countries, and there are views of foreign scholars on this. In the sociology of foreign countries there are several definitions of the concept of "the youth". Ensuring the social interests of the youth is also unique in the

experience of foreign countries, especially in the United States, where high opportunities for youth education have been created. It was noted that the development of higher education in the country has become a key socio-economic priority: the state's target allocations have reached a record level. Such a choice was due to two main reasons. First, it contributes to growing economic growth and labor productivity on an increasingly dynamic scale. Second, encouraging higher education provides a strong foundation for improving the well-being and income of the population".[1]

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

For instance, in China, it constantly takes care of the youth by creating conditions for them to receive quality education at home and abroad. The youth are constantly supported by the state to find a permanent and effective job, to open their opportunities, to realize their creative potential. It is unfortunate that the youth in China, in turn, do not see themselves as passive consumers of the achievements and privileges of their predecessors, but rather strive to act as a responsible generation of their ancestors. According to R. Alimov, "the modern generation of Chinese youth faces a huge task – to make a significant contribution to the creation of a modern developed state, to make the "Chinese dream" a reality".[2]

In our country, the social significance of the phenomenon of the youth, who are now widely involved in everyday life in the socio-legal, economic-political, cultural and educational spheres, showing examples of activeness in all spheres of society. At present, with a focus on the development of society, concrete results have been achieved with reforms aimed at science, education, upbringing, attention to youth and the gradual modernization of society. The modern life demands flexibility, advanced thinking, innovative approaches from people, especially from the youth. Therefore, activeness of the youth is a criteria for national development and sustainable development of civil society.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a act of supreme legal force in the protection of the rights of the youth, which, in addition to the norms that apply to all citizens, also contains rules that apply to the youth. In particular, Article 41 states: "Everyone has the right to education. Free general education is guaranteed by the state. School work is under state control"; Article 45 states: "The rights of adolescents, the disabled and the lonely elderly are protected by the state"; Article 64 states: "Parents are obliged to support and bring up

their children until they reach adulthood”; Article 66 sets out the norms: “Adult, able-bodied children are obliged to take care of their parents”.[3]

Ensuring the rights and interests of the youth as an important social level in society is interrelated with the satisfaction of their material and spiritual needs in society. This means that the youth are an important source of social life and its perfection, giving it a special charm and strength. Another thing to keep in mind is that under the influence of globalization, scientific and technological progress, the forms of youth welfare will change, its place in social life will be determined depending on its behavior in society.

Ensuring the interests of the youth is the most important priority of our state policy. According to scientists, “Creating conditions for the comprehensive development and upbringing of the younger generation has been a priority of state policy in the interests of the youth since the early years of independence of Uzbekistan. This is a future-oriented investment, as 40 percent of the country’s population is under the age of 18 and 64 percent is under the age of 30”.[3]

The material interests of the youth in society depend more on their social needs. Social needs create spiritual values that shape the youth’s sense of satisfaction with life. Social needs are very diverse: entrepreneurial and economic relationships, deep friendships with those around them, professional development and self-expression, striving to make people happy, building respect for society and its members, helping those in need.

On 11th March, 2021 the Resolution No. 132 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures for social support of the youth” was adopted. According to the resolution, a youth support fund was established, which is included in the “Youth notebook”. Fund provides financial assistance to the disadvantaged youth included in the “Youth notebook”, for instance it helps to cover 75% of the cost of entrepreneurship and vocational training of the youth, to purchase equipment and tools to start a business and self-employment, it is aimed at allocating subsidies for the payment of up to 50% of the tuition fee of the youth of families included in the “Iron notebook” studying in higher education institutions of the country.[5]

In our society, in the important work of supporting the youth, great attention is paid to solve social problems in their lives. The study and solution of the youth problems is of great importance not only in theory but also in practice. This direction provides them with practical

assistance in the process of solving problems in the state and society – from small to large-scale problems of age, with its real indicators. In this process, the youth will have the opportunity to solve their problems on a modern and innovative basis, based on the regions, demographic conditions and socio-economic conditions, as well as to predict their positive results.

CONCLUSION

Taking into account the fact that the participation of the youth is an important feature in the context of national development, the following innovative proposals help to realize their vital interests and needs, solve social problems, create decent working conditions for them:

- organization of the innovative process of ensuring the social interests of the youth, who are the main level of social life of society, and in this process their innovative thinking, innovative resources, innovative initiatives, innovative potential should be developed;

- organization of job fairs called “Entrepreneur – is reliance of the country” aimed at vocational guidance, employment, formation of entrepreneurial skills of temporarily unemployed and unorganized youth living in mahallas, holding a competition “My land is my wealth” in order to attract unorganized youth to entrepreneurship;

- organization of sports clubs (fitness, gym, tennis, football fields, swimming pools, chess) in rural areas and mahallas for the purpose of meaningful organization of leisure time of unorganized youth;

- organization of modern innovative cultural venues, parks, concert halls, cinemas in districts and rural centers for the youth, organization of visits to “Mobile youth theater studios” for unorganized youth in mahallas;

- meaningful organization of leisure time of unorganized youth, organization of monthly trips to large enterprises, factories and plants in the region in order to ensure their employment.

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LEGAL ISSUES OF APPLICATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY IN INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION

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ABSTRACT: This article examines current issues regarding confidentiality in international commercial arbitration, role of confidentiality as advantage of arbitration before litigation. Adopting unified rules in national laws would solve current problems.

KEYWORDS: international commercial arbitration, litigation, privacy, confidentiality, arbitration rules, national law.

INTRODUCTION

International commercial arbitration has a number of advantages before litigation. Comparing to litigation in national courts arbitration proceedings are mostly cheaper and faster, less formal in nature of procedure than the rules of procedure in national courts. Among other advantages are elements of privacy and confidentiality of the arbitration proceedings, and the ability of the parties to manage the course of the proceedings. In addition, parties can not only choose an arbitrator, but appoint an arbitrator with special knowledge to resolve the issue, unlike in state courts, where the judge is appointed by the state. Its weaknesses include the lack of a complete set of preliminary information and the limited availability of cross-examination of testimony, the impossibility - or extreme difficulty - of appealing an award, and the lack of a guarantee of confidentiality in all cases.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Arbitral proceedings, in contrast to court proceedings, were generally more secretive, as their decisions were not published. In other words, many parties prefer arbitration to litigation precisely because they do not want the subject of their dispute to become known to anyone. However, the duty of confidentiality is often not guaranteed and, in most legal systems it is not

protected by law.

The parties enter into a confidentiality agreement in order to better protect the preservation of confidentiality of the arbitration, all documents related to it and the award. However, the confidentiality agreement itself does not give the parties any guarantees of protection. Confidentiality agreements can also be breached because there is no absolute guarantee of confidentiality and because arbitration between private parties - even though a private proceeding is not opened publicly, unlike a litigation - is a proceeding whose privacy and confidentiality can be subject to different threats. For example, the confidentiality of an arbitration may be threatened by the media or other scrutiny. In addition, although the confidentiality agreement binds the parties with an obligation, it does not apply to other persons who have not signed it, who will have to participate and witness the arbitration process. It is not always possible to force all non-signatories to enter into such agreements. Such factors may cause parties to opt out of arbitration as a means of resolving a dispute. Confidentiality of arbitration proceedings has also always depended on factors not related to the arbitration itself. Courts may appoint the same arbitrator for two or more similar cases to ensure consistent results and thus make all relevant documents and transcripts from one proceeding available in the next. Courts also play an important role in challenging or enforcing arbitral awards, and any decision taken by a tribunal can become public.

The number of competing values makes it difficult for any legislative solution to be effective enough to address the confidentiality issue under all circumstances. However, several arbitration institutions have adopted confidentiality rules, which generally aim to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of litigation, subject to the consent of the parties and any legal disclosure obligation applied. However, not all arbitration rules address confidentiality.

Some scholars believe that confidentiality should be enshrined in arbitration rules, but not in the Model Law. The inclusion of a confidentiality clause in the Model Law would surely be a step forward. But the most effective way to achieve a unified mechanism for regulating confidentiality in international commercial arbitration would be to implement confidentiality rules in national arbitration laws.

First, enshrining privacy rules in national laws will end disputes over the existence of an implied duty of confidentiality. The norm of the legislation will become mandatory for all participants in the arbitration proceedings.

Second, institutional arbitration rules are only binding on parties to arbitration institutions and

arbitrators. Like *lex arbitri*, national arbitration laws will also be binding on attorneys and third parties like witnesses and experts, third-party sponsors and translators. Thus, introducing confidentiality provisions into national arbitration laws will solve the problem of the obligation to maintain the confidentiality of third parties.

Third, unlike the confidentiality clauses in the arbitration rules, the confidentiality clauses in national laws will apply to all arbitration proceedings. Confidentiality clauses, when enshrined in the arbitration rules, will not be able to provide a uniform approach, since they do not apply to ad hoc arbitrations. On the contrary, national law is used in all arbitrations.

CONCLUSION

A unified approach to the confidentiality of international commercial arbitration is possible. The best way to do this is to harmonize national arbitration laws. This will benefit all users of arbitration and more generally the public by increasing the legal predictability and transparency of arbitration.

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IMPROVING THE ACCURACY OF COMPENSATING DEVICES POWER CONTROL AT RAILWAY PARTITIONING POSTS

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ABSTRACT: We considered the power control of the compensation device in traction power supply at the partition station. It was proposed to estimate the load rate of the traction network and then adjust the power of the compensating device by the loss of voltage between the traction substation and the partition station. Power losses in the traction network with a compensating device at the partition station are determined in matrix form. It was also proposed to estimate the load rate of the traction network and to adjust the power of the compensating device by the voltage loss between the traction substation and the partition station.

KEYWORDS: Traction network, partition station, traction substation, compensating device, matrix form, power coefficient.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, much attention is paid to the program for the development of speed and high-speed electric transport in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The AC electric rolling stock (ERS) consumes active and reactive currents, of which the first is to create mechanical energy of traction motors, and the second is to magnetize transformers and reactors of electric locomotives. In this regard, the tension

on railway lines is reduced. Therefore, to increase voltage and in particular power, it is envisaged to install compensating devices (CS), which can be installed at traction substations or at partition posts in the middle of the railway section [1].

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Consider the power loss with the compensating device at the partition station (PS).

They are equal in matrix form:

$$\Delta P = \underline{I}^T \cdot \underline{R} \cdot \underline{I}. \quad (1)$$

here $\underline{I} = |I_1, I_2, \dots, I_k|$ – is ERS and CS current column vector (I_k);

R – is square matrix of contact network nodal active resistances;

$\underline{I}^T$ – is conjugated and transposed current value.

For determining the minimum power loss from (1), we calculate the derivative of dP/dI_k , equating it to zero. We get the condition of minimum losses in the traction network:

$$I_k \cdot R_{kk} = \sum (I_{pi} \cdot R_{ik}), \quad (2)$$

This means that the voltage loss up to the CS at the node active resistance R_{kk} from the CS current should be equal to the voltage loss from the traction load reactive currents I_{pi} to the CC.

At PS voltage is measured with the help of voltage transformer VT, which determines voltage of partition station.

Therefore, the voltage losses in the traction network from the traction substation to the PS are equal to:

$$\Delta U = U_o - U_{pc} \quad (3)$$

here U_o – is voltage at traction substation feeders.

If the CS on the PS is switched on, then in this case, the voltage loss to the PS will be:

$$\Delta U_{nc(k)} = U_o - U_{nc(k)} \quad (4)$$

The indexes (k) mean that the CS is functioning.

Voltage losses in traction network ΔU_{nc} from traction load are equal to [2].

$$\Delta U_{nc} = \sum (I_p \cdot R_{ik} + I_q \cdot X_{ik}) = \sum I_i \cdot (\cos \varphi \cdot R_{ik} + \sin \varphi \cdot X_{ik}) =$$

$$\left(\sum I_i R_{ik}\right) \cdot (\cos \varphi + q \sin \varphi) = \left(\sum I_i R_{ik}\right) \cdot a \quad (5)$$

here I_p, I_q are active and reactive components of traction load currents, may say that the traction load $\cos \varphi$ equal to each other.

$(\cos \varphi \cdot R_{ik} + \sin \varphi \cdot X_{ik}) = Z_{ik(n)}$ – is impedance [2] and is used in calculations of traction power supply with CS.

Divide $Z_{ik(n)}$ to R_{ik} , then the value $a = Z_{ik(n)} / R_{ik} = (\cos \varphi + q \sin \varphi)$ is the relative value of impedance.

In engineering case calculations $\cos \varphi$ for electric trains are equal, and $q = X_{ik} / R_{ik} = \text{const}$, in this case it can be considered that $a = \text{const}$ for all substation areas.

It can be seen from (5) that the voltage loss is determined by the measured voltage loss ΔU_{nc} .

$$\sum I_i R_{ik} = \Delta U_{nc} / a \quad (6)$$

For reactive current $\cos \varphi = 0, \sin \varphi = 1$, in this case voltage loss to CS from its reactive current at single-sided power supply of PS are $I_k X_{kk}$. With the measured current, it is possible to calculate these voltage losses at X_{kk} .

Voltage losses from reactive loads are calculated from measured voltage losses from traction load without CS.

$$\sum I_{pi} R_{ik} = \Delta U_{nc} (\cos \varphi) / a \quad (7)$$

When calculating the value of $\sum I_{pi} R_{ik}$, it is necessary to measure ΔU_{nc} , which can be multiplied by $\cos \varphi / a$.

Voltage loss $\sum I_{pi} R_{ik}$ at operating CS can be found:

$$\sum I_{pi} R_{ik} = \Delta U_{nc(k)} (\cos \varphi) / a \quad (8)$$

Since the partition point is located in the middle of the railway line, we find an expression for impedance:

$$Z_{ik(n)} = 2,775 \cdot \cos \varphi + 7,2 \cdot \sin \varphi$$

The obtained CS power is compared with $0,5 Q_{ko} = 2,75 \text{ Mvar}$. Data are in the Table 1.

Table 1.

Experience No	CS position	Voltage drop to partition station ΔU , kV	Voltage loss to partition station ΔU , kV	Voltage at substation/partition station (by voltmeter readings), kV	Current value of reasonable CS power calculated by voltage drop/loss, Q _k	Control signal CS
1	off	0,983+i0,612	0,77	27,75 / 26,8	1,802/1,579	Without control
2	off	3,276+i2,039	2,82	24,8/21,98	3,106/2,794	On

It can be seen from Table 1 that at low load the CS remains switched off and at high load the CS can be switched on.

The comparative error in the calculations for the drop and for the voltage losses can be a fraction of percent. The main error in the calculations of the required power of the CS is in the calculations with the value $\cos\varphi$ ($\sin\varphi$).

On the stretches of the railway sections, the traction load power factor varies within narrow limits [1] and in this regard, errors can be calculated when the traction load current phase changes from 29° to 45° .

In case of traction current equal to 300 A at PS, the current value of CS power calculated from voltage losses can vary from 3.757 to 2.548 Mvar. In this case, the error will be up to 22%.

With an increase in the accuracy of controlling the power of the CS, the reliability of power supply to electric trains will increase due to an improvement in the voltage mode and a decrease in electricity losses in traction power supply.

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HOME GROWN SKIN SAFEGUARD AND PICTURE SAFEGUARD COMBINATION: A VICTIM ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

solar bright sort b radiations is on a very basic level responsible to be consumed by keratinocytes prompting creation of free revolutionaries or receptive oxygen species receptive oxygen species which may cause skin erythema, burn from the sun, skin malignancy and untimely maturing. home grown sunscreen watch skin from sun's radiations which lessens burns from the sun with diminished danger of skin hurts. enemies of oxidants extinguish free revolutionaries and receptive oxygen species which may help photograph security impact. this audit accumulated recently licensed home grown photograph insurance pieces and skin safeguard.

KEYWORDS: skin erythema; sunscreen; picture safeguard.

INTRODUCTION

Solar bright radiations at the world's surface incorporate around 96-97 % uva and 2-5 % uvb. the recurrence of bright sort b is on a very basic level obligated to be consumed by keratinocytes prompting creation of free extremists or receptive oxygen species receptive oxygen species which may cause skin erythema, burn from the sun, skin disease and untimely maturing [1,2]. enemies of oxidants extinguish free revolutionaries and receptive oxygen species which may help photograph security impact. home grown sunscreen effective items watch skin from sun's radiations which lessens burns from the sun with

diminished danger of skin hurts. this survey accumulated recently licensed natural photograph insurance structures and skin protection. hardly any natural photograph protectants.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

A top notch sunscreen should ingest or puzzle out the burn from the sun emanation causing and should be non-poisonous and non-disturbing. it ought to be steady under air, light and dampness. additionally, it should be tolerably non-unpredictable, accordingly won't vanish . natural sun security syntheses and skin safeguard licensed for protected for sunscreen and photograph insurance action has been recorded in separately.

CONCLUSION

This victim audit includes recently licensed home grown photograph assurance creations and skin safeguard which are significant to deflect skin harm brought about by intense or steady exposure to sunlight based uv radiations. this victim survey was conveyed utilizing the catchphrases home grown sunscreen, photograph insurance and photograph maturing.

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REFORMS TO REDUCE THE BUREAUCRATIC BARRIERS

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ABSTRACT: this article discusses the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan to reduce bureaucratic obstacles, as well as the relaxation for citizens, their importance and relevance, which are set out in the presidential decree adopted on March 23, 2021.

KEYWORDS: population and business entities, bureaucratic obstacles, Civil Status, birth, marriage, divorce from marriage, death, change of name and surname, birth and adoption.

INTRODUCTION

It is not an exaggeration to say that the reforms carried out in our country in recent years consist in providing public services to the population on the ground floor, creating convenience and comfort for the population and business entities in general.

In particular, over the past two years, a number of legislative acts have been adopted aimed at limiting various types of overarching and bureaucracy in the relations between the population and state bodies, further improving the system of providing public services to individuals and legal entities.

As an example, we can say these normative documents: the law "On amendments and additions to some legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the further reduction of bureaucratic obstacles and the introduction of modern management principles into the activities of state bodies and organizations" dated September 28, 2020, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for further reduction of bureaucratic obstacles and introduction of modern management principles into the activities of state bodies and organizations" dated December 9, 2019, № PF-4546, "On additional measures to create more favorable conditions for the use of public services to the population and business entities, to reduce bureaucratic obstacles in this regard" dated March 23, 2021, № PF-6191 [1-3].

When you get acquainted with the decree № PF-6191, it can be seen that it literally eliminated a lot of bureaucratic obstacles that tormented the population, put an end to the fact that the population and entrepreneurs walk in the direction of the administration.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In particular, the decree provides for a number of measures to reduce excessive procedures and bureaucratic obstacles in the provision of public services to the population and business entities.

In the decree, from June 1, 2021, it was established that 7 types of Civil Status Acts (birth, marriage, divorce from marriage, death, change of name and surname, birth and adoption) should be recorded, medical examination of married persons and registration of biometric passport abroad should be carried out on the ecsterritorial principle. That is, citizens can now perform actions on the above listed cases in the desired territory. For example, if a citizen named A, who is on a permanent list in the city of Navoi, works in the city of Tashkent, it will be possible to register a marriage in the same place itself.

Also, with this decree, it was established that all information related to the records of the act of civil status in the implementation of notarial acts should be obtained by the notary public independently, without requiring excessive information from citizens, through the information system of the unified electronic archive of the FHDYO (it means: state body for writing acts of civil status).

According to the decree, overpaid payments in the use of services through the Centers of public services will be returned by the agency of public services in one working day. The funds returned in this are collected from the appropriate organization (without the participation of a citizen). This put an end to the fact that the citizens are in charge of the state office in this matter.

Also another important issue in the decree, From May 1, 2021 an application for the registration of a biometric passport abroad-the application form and payment of state duty are electronically accepted through the single interactive portal of State Services. Another important news is that, starting from June 1, 2021, when issuing an ID card to persons under 16 years of age, their registration as a taxpayer and in the accumulative pension system is carried

out simultaneously. This procedure creates relief for citizens and eliminates excessive overexertion.

In practice, the registration of documents related to the recording of the death of a person took a long time. Now, in accordance with the procedure established by this decree, the functions of the ministries of Internal Affairs, Defense, Foreign Affairs, health, employment and Labor Relations, the state tax office, the extra-budgetary pension fund and the agency of public services were clearly defined in the formalization of documents related to the deceased person.

That is, the appointment of a one-time pension for the funeral of a deceased person is carried out electronically. Family members of the deceased are not required to be present, for example, they are not required to provide documentation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this decree became a document that facilitates and modernizes the provision of public services in our country, improves the quality of life of the population, investment climate, working environment, serves business development and sharply reduces bureaucracy.

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SELF-GOVERNMENT OF CITIZENS – THE BASIS OF THE CONSTITUTIONAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: information about the time detained by the detention of persons detained by the detention, detention and detention of persons detained by the detention of persons detained.

KEYWORDS: Constitution, democratic legal state, the right to self-government, self-governing bodies.

INTRODUCTION

In the following years in the world, at a time when the system of self-government of citizens is recognized as the lowest stage of Management, an integral sign of a Democratic state and a kind of social management of society, the improvement of national legislation regulating this system and its role and importance in the system of mass management are becoming. Therefore, priority directions for further improvement of the effectiveness of reforms carried out in the strategy of actions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the revision of the activities of the self-governing bodies of citizens in the process of improving public administration have been established. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh. M.Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, said that “the results of our reforms, the ongoing changes and the mood of the population will first be felt in the neighborhood. In this sense, the mirror of our neighborhood – light and conscience, if we say so, will be correct,¹” calls for further reform of the system of self-government of citizens.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

¹ President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Mirizyoev's address to the Supreme Assembly on December 29, 2020, <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>.

At the level of living standards of the population, the conditions in the neighborhoods, the quality of infrastructure and services are an important factor, the results of reforms and changes in the sectors are also felt first in the neighborhood. Therefore, in the appeal of the head of state to the Oliy Majlis, the leaders of all levels went down and said that work on their field should be organized in the neighborhoods, studying the problems and finding solutions to them. At the same time, initiatives were put forward to expand the competence of the neighborhood office, improve the material supply of the chairman and employees.

The right to self-government as a legal structure does not fall into the sentence of the main branches of law. When determining its place in the system of Public Administration, it should be taken into account that it is a derivative structure that arose as a result of the development of the right to self - government, in connection with its separation in the system of society and public administration, as well as on the basis of the development of special legislation on.

It should be recognized that the norms of self-government are reflected in a number of articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, the norms of self-government, enshrined in Articles 32 and 105 of the Constitution, are one of the foundations of the constitutional system. In particular, according to Article 32 of the Constitution, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to participate directly in the management of public and state affairs, as well as through their representatives. Such participation will be entrusted to AML by self-government, holding referendums and democratically organizing state bodies, as well as by developing and improving public control over the activities of state bodies.

Consequently, self-government, which is one of the foundations of the constitutional system, is the most important principle of the organization and implementation of power in society and the state, this principle, along with other constitutional principles, determines the democratic system of governance and the foundations of legal statehood in our country. In addition, in accordance with Article 105 of the Constitution, self-governing bodies of citizens in towns, villages and ovules, as well as in the neighborhoods in which they are located, as well as in the neighborhoods in which they are located, elect the chairman.

Accordingly, the population of towns, villages and ovules, as well as the neighborhoods of cities, is recognized as the main subjects of self-management. It is also not surprising that

the right to self-government is exercised by citizens directly, as well as through their elected representatives.

Another of the tasks of self-government is to raise the social and economic potential of its territories to a high level, based on the principals of decentralized governance of democracy and power, independently resolving issues of local significance².

The transition from centralized management in a Democratic state to decentralized management means that the population has the right to participate in the management of the state kengaytiradi, decentralized management in relation to centralized management gives a more positive result, since the population living in this territory knows its territory, that is, the territory knows first of all what is necessary, what problem it.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, self-government is the basis of any constitutional system, which in itself expresses the will of the people and ensures the approximation of the population to the management of the state. Self-government implies the performance of work of local importance by citizens both directly and indirectly within the framework of law, but without the intervention of the central authority.

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THE MAIN POINTS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN “ON INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION”

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ABSTRACT: On February 16, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the Law "On International Commercial Arbitration"(the"Law"). As a result, Uzbekistan became the 85th country and 118th jurisdiction to adopt legislation based on the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration (hereinafter referred to as the "UNCITRAL Model Law").

KEYWORDS: International Commercial Arbitration, equal opportunities, arbitration proceedings.

INTRODUCTION

This thesis will provide a brief overview of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On International Commercial Arbitration", highlighting a number of its key provisions.

The purpose of the adoption of this Law is to regulate legal relations in the field of international commercial arbitration. Regarding the scope of application, this Law applies to international commercial arbitration activities by virtue of agreements in force between Uzbekistan and other States. Commercial disputes from contractual and non-contractual relations, subject to the international commercial arbitration .

If the actions (inactions) in connection with the arbitration proceedings of the arbitrators, experts, the arbitral tribunal, the arbitration institution and its employees do not show signs of an intentional nature, then they are not liable to the parties or other persons of the arbitration proceedings.

The activities of arbitration courts are independent and impartial.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

According to the requirements of this Law, the conclusion of an arbitration agreement between the parties for the settlement of a dispute allows the parties to submit an application to the court in which the application was filed for the issue that was the subject of the arbitration agreement and the court must, no matter which of the parties requests this no later than the submission of its own first appeal on the fact of the dispute, send the parties to arbitration .

The Parties are given the opportunity to determine the number of arbitrators at their own discretion. In the absence of this, three arbitrators-judges are appointed.

If there is a request from the parties, the arbitral tribunal may take temporary interim measures to secure the claim, by which, until the final decision is made, the arbitral tribunal has an order that one of the parties:

1) maintain or restore the situation that exists or existed before the settlement of the dispute;

2) take measures to prevent current or imminent harm, or harm to the arbitration itself, or refrain from taking measures that may cause such harm;

3) provide funds for the purpose of preserving the assets at the expense of which the subsequent award of the arbitration should be executed;

4) retain evidence relevant to the case and essential to settle the dispute . The parties are given the opportunity to submit, without notifying any other, a preliminary order ordering any party not to prejudice the purposes in accordance with the interim measures. a party requesting the order of a temporary interim measure of protection declaring the issuance of a preliminary order ordering a party not to prejudice the purposes in accordance with the interim measure of protection.

Interim measures are prescribed in connection with arbitration proceedings, regardless of the place of arbitration, in accordance with the procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and taking into account the specifics of international arbitration . The interim measure of the arbitral tribunal is binding and is enforced by applying to the national court .

The parties are given equal opportunities, and each party has a reasonable opportunity to present its position.

In addition, the parties may, at their sole discretion, agree on the place of arbitration. In the absence of this agreement, the place of arbitration is subject to determination by the arbitral tribunal taking into account the circumstances of the case and the convenience factor.

Further, the parties may, at their discretion, agree on the language of the arbitration. If there is no such consistency, the definition of the language is subject to the court, which is acceptable to use in the proceedings of the case .

The dispute is subject to resolution by the rules of law chosen by the parties as applicable to the merits of the dispute. If the parties themselves settle the dispute by reaching an agreement in the course of the arbitration, the arbitral tribunal has the right to terminate the arbitration .

The form of the award is written and is made by the sole arbitrator or arbitrators. An appeal to the court against an arbitration decision may be made only by filing an application for annulment . The court may set aside the award if:

1. There is an incapacity of one of the parties;
2. Invalidity of the agreement under the law to which the parties have submitted
3. Ignorance of the parties about the appointment of an arbitrator or about the arbitration proceedings
4. Making an arbitration decision on a dispute that is not provided for resolution in arbitration
5. The arbitral tribunal or the arbitration procedure is not inherent in the agreement of the parties.

Also, if the court determines that:

1. Non-compliance of the subject matter of the dispute with arbitration proceedings under the law of Uzbekistan;
2. contradiction of the arbitration award to the public policy of Uzbekistan;

The arbitral award, regardless of the place of its adoption, is recognized as binding and, upon filing a written application with the court, is enforced .

This law will help to make Uzbekistan a reliable place for dispute resolution in the Central Asian region and beyond. It is also an important legal event for Uzbekistan, as it will help Uzbekistan attract foreign investment in infrastructure, human capital, and the development of tourism and other important economic sectors. The law will also help boost

investor confidence and the business climate, reduce the cost of doing business, and improve Uzbekistan's international standing in various indices and rankings.

This Law comes into force after 6 months from the date of its official publication.

For the full functioning of this law, it is planned to make appropriate changes to the Economic Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the relevant laws.

It is hoped that this law will be applied by the Uzbek judicial system in such a way as to demonstrate Uzbekistan's pro-arbitration approach to the international arbitration community. Among other things, it will promote the Tashkent International Arbitration Center, established in Uzbekistan in 2018 by Presidential Decree No. 4001 of November 5, 2018, as a regional arbitration center.

CONCLUSION

In general, the adoption of this law is a significant step in the development of arbitration in Uzbekistan and a long-awaited tool for the arbitration community in Uzbekistan and beyond. The adoption of this law contributes to ensuring an effective legal regime for the settlement of international commercial disputes in Uzbekistan.

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IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE RESPECTS AND STRUCTURE OF ACTION OF B-GLUCANS

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ABSTRACT

β -glucans are found in bacterial and fungal cellwalls and have been ensnared in the inception of against microbial immuneresponse. β -glucan sact onDectin-1, complementreceptor (CR3) and TLR-2/6 immunereceptors. They trigger a gathering of immune cell sincludingmacrophages, neutrophils, monocytes, natural killer cells and dendritic cells. Most β -glucansenter the proximalsmallintestine and some are caught by the macrophages. They are disguised and divided inside the cells, then transported by the macrophages to the marrow and endothelial reticular framework. The small β -glucansfragments are eventually released by the macrophages and taken up by other immune cells leading to various immune responses.

KEYWORDS: β -glucans, immuneresponse, B-cell, lymphocytes , macrophages.

INTRODUCTION

Immune stimulator spromote activation of invulnerable framework cells directly or by implication .They can increase cell proliferation and cell differentiation. They alter the separation of innocent CD4+Thprecursors in Th1 or Th2 cells .There by modulate the Thctokine type production by changing the balance of cell-interceded and humor alimmunity just as the class or subclass of immunoglobulin synthesis . They can actuate the complementary complement pathway , bringing about the accompanying immune stimulatory effects: supporting the introduction of the T-cellantigen stimulation of B-cells by B-cell co-receptors upon direct show of the B-cellantigen helping the capacity of

dendritic cells to preserve B-cell memory and in this manner improves the optional antibody response age of other immune stimulators. They are immune stimulators with

- 1 Microbial beginning β -glucans, peptidoglucans, LPS, chitosan, chitin, FCA/Freund's complete adjuvant, etc.
- 2 .Plant origin β -glucans, polysaccharides, alginate, etc.
- 3 .Synthetic is oprinosine, lemamizole, FK 565 muramylpeptide, MDP/muramyl dipeptide etc.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The impact of β -glucan has for quite some time been demonstrated to protect against bacteria, infections and pathogenic microorganisms. As of late, various examinations have demonstrated anti-tumour impact by activating antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity .Because of these properties, β -glucans are called modifiers of the biological response. The main targets of β -glucans are macrophages and dendritic cells, albeit the impact on neutrophils, T-and B-lymphocytes, NK cells is additionally depicted. Their immunosuppressive properties are primarily related to the enactment of macrophages, their cytotoxic movement and the creation of inflammatory cytokines. They likewise increment the phenotypic and useful development of dendritic cells . Their impact on T-lymphocyte activation is roundabout, basically by IL-12 and IFN- γ , delivered by activated macrophages and dendritic cells. Increased NK-mediated cytotoxicity under β -glucan action has been shown in vitro and in vivo

Instrument of Action Most β -glucans enter the proximal part of the small intestine and are captured by the macrophages, where they are disguised and divided. They are shipped from them to the bone marrow and the reticulo-endothelial framework. Small fragments are confined from macrophages and taken up by the circulating granulocytes, monocytes and dendritic cells. The immune response then be evoked . Most β -glucans are accepted to activate both non-explicit and explicit immune responses as most immune stimulators. A fundamental element of their activity, notwithstanding, is the absence of polarization of the immune response to Th-1 or Th-2. Recent studies in experimental models show an expansion in administrative T lymphocytes T-reg under the activity of β -glucans.

This significant circumstance expands the opportunities for their application without potential risks of autoimmunity.

CONCLUSION

β -glucans are a promising gathering of immune stimulators whose since a long time ago realized exactly demonstrated properties are affirmed in modern experimental studies. Future clinical studies will expand our knowledge of their part as therapeutics in the immune protection of the human body.

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HISTORY OF FORMATION OF THE INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC SERVICE

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ABSTRACT: The author examines the historical period of the formation and further development of the institute of public service through the prism of the experience of foreign countries. Also, the paper presents some factors that influenced the choice of a certain model of the institution of public service by a certain state. In addition, the author analyzes the features of two methods of completing the state apparatus – the "merit system" and the "spoils system".

KEYWORDS: Civil service, model, state apparatus, "merit system", "spoils system".

INTRODUCTION

The history of the formation of the institution of civil service has passed a long evolutionary path of its development. Any individual state built its own model of public administration, in particular the civil service system, based on the specific features of the internal political situation. From historical experience, we can understand what factors the states relied on when choosing a model of civil service that would ideally merge with their chosen political course and how effectively this model would allow this state to realize its primary goals and objectives.

So, here are some of the factors that influenced the choice of a certain model by a certain state:

First, these are the distinctive features of historical development. This factor implies the emergence of a primitive institution of civil service, the consolidation of its activities, terms of reference, spheres of influence, organizational form at the normative level and its further progressive development.

It should be emphasized that the first countries where the institution of civil service emerged were Germany and France. It was in these states that the primary fundamental elements of the European model of civil service were born. These elements include the normative and legal consolidation of this institution, the unification of norms, strict vertical power, etc.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In England, for example, the concept of "public service" was not used in everyday life, not to mention the consolidation of this institution at the highest level. The role of the civil service was performed by the so-called "semi-amateur administration". Public service in the country was something like a gift of power from the royal family, which, like the power of the monarch, could even be inherited. Subsequently, in England, this system was reformed and modified, which ultimately led to the adoption of appropriate regulatory legal acts in the country, securing the status of the institution of public service. This event took place only at the end of the 19th century.

Secondly, these are the characteristic features of the legal system of countries. As you know, there are several legal systems in the world, but two of them - Anglo-Saxon and Romano-Germanic - stand out from the rest with their specific approaches.

Countries based on Anglo-Saxon law do not have a consolidated system of legislation in the context of the institution of civil service. In countries of the Romano-Germanic structure, the emphasis is understandably placed on the normative consolidation of this institution. Moreover, the activities of state bodies and civil servants are accordingly regulated by the Basic Law and relevant laws.

Thirdly, these are the peculiarities of the state structure of countries. Based on this, the scientist M.E. Apon identifies the following models of public service:

- 1) Centralized closed model implemented in a unitary state;
- 2) A relatively decentralized closed model implemented in a federal state;
- 3) Relatively decentralized open model implemented in a unitary state;
- 4) Decentralized open model implemented in a federal state .

Scientist A.V. Rassokhin in his work, considering each of these models, studied their characteristic features and analyzed how they influenced the development of the institution of public service in developed countries. So, according to his version of the closed model, mainly European countries adhere. This model has the following features:

- 1) the subordinate organization of the civil service system, detailed regulatory regulation of the competence of each level of the civil service;
- 2) a "closed" system of recruiting personnel for the civil service;
- 3) high legal and social status of civil servants, in which job growth, wages and benefits mainly depend on the length of service in the civil service and the position held;
- 4) complicated procedure for the dismissal of civil servants.

France and Germany are striking examples of a centralized closed model in a unitary state and a relatively decentralized closed model in a federal state.

In France, a centralized, closed model began to take shape during the French Revolution (1789-1799). Among the characteristic features of this model, one can single out a strict vertical hierarchy through the prism of the system of subordination of local government bodies to a single center; a system for selecting potential civil servants on a competitive basis, etc.

Considering the state of affairs in Germany as an adherent of a decentralized closed model, we can conclude that in the system of the institution of civil service in the country, a special role is assigned to political parties in terms of resolving personnel issues and improving the institution of political appointments. Among the characteristic features of this model, we can single out the stable social guarantees of a civil servant in the performance of his service; appointing to positions of potential civil servants from among graduates of higher educational institutions, distinguished by high productivity and academic performance in the process of study; strict delimitation in the distribution of powers between subjects of public service, etc.

The open model is characterized by a transparent system of recruiting potential civil servants based on a fair competitive selection system; the predominance of cadres with a general humanitarian mindset; a fairly simple procedure for dismissal from office.

Scientist M.E. Apon cites Great Britain as an example as a country adhering to a relatively decentralized open model in a unitary state, while, in his opinion, the decentralized open model in a federal state is embodied by the institution of the US civil service.

Thus, in Great Britain, a large-scale reform of the civil service began with the Northcote-Trevelyan policy report to the British Parliament in 1854. In the course of the reform, the civil service system was unified: three classes of employees were introduced - administrators, executors and clerks), highly qualified personnel came to the service. The completion of the reform can be considered the introduction in 1870 of open competitive examinations, conducted under the supervision of the Central Examination Commission (Civil Service Commission).

In the United States, the institution of civil service also emerged in a specific way. The "victor's spoils system", introduced in 1829 by President E. Jackson, became widespread - the positions were received by representatives of the winning party. The end of the XIX - the beginning of the XX century is characterized by the need to introduce in the United States a "rational" model of civil service of the European type. During this period, a unified system of posts, salaries and qualification examinations was introduced for a significant part of civil servants, which dealt a blow to the "victor's spoils system". This, in turn, laid a solid foundation for the further development of the institution of public service in the United States.

CONCLUSION

Historically, there have been two methods of staffing the state apparatus - the so-called "merit system" and "mining system". The merit system provides that only those who have proven their professional suitability and defeated all their opponents in a competitive selection for a certain place in the public administration system hold public positions. The mining system, in turn, presupposes the fact that a person who won the official elections for top leadership positions, or who seized the current power in his own hands illegally, acquires the right to appoint to significant public positions those who supported him and in every possible way contributed to him coming to power. Such patterns were very often traced in the historical period of the development of the institution of public service and continue to this day.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF CITIES DURING THE KUSHAN EMPIRE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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ABSTARCT: The article examines the history of statehood in the ancient Kushan Empire and its significance for the Great Silk Road. The study focuses on the study of the history of the cities of the Kushan Empire as a basis for the development of modern tourism.

KEYWORD: Kushan empire, borders of the Kushan state, historical and architectural monuments, archaeological and tourist forum, center of international tourism.

INTRODUCTION

Kushan Empire ... Why are we talking about the Kushan state? Why do we focus on the cities of the Kushan Empire in the development of tourism? One of the main reasons for this is that the history of the Great Silk Road dates back to the Kushan Empire. Given that the essence of tourism is travel, the Great Ipal Road can be considered the beginning of the earliest trade trips. Due to the large number of historical archeological monuments dating back to the Kushan period, we have the opportunity to develop a large-scale development of archeological tourism in these areas.

The Kushan Empire is an ancient state that existed in Central Asia in the 1st-4th centuries AD. The Kushan state came into being in the first half of the first century AD as a result of the rise of Kushan, one of the emirates of the Yuezhi state. The term “Kushan” refers to either a dynasty or a tribe and was first used on coins minted by King Geray, who ruled in the late 1st century BC - early 1st century AD. The first Kushan possessions included Northern Bactria (Tajikistan and southern Uzbekistan, southeastern Turkmenistan). Kushan is pronounced Guishuan in Chinese and is probably the name of one of the Yuezhi

tribes. The ruler was Yabgu (Amir). According to historical sources, the Kushan state was founded by Kudzula Kadfiz, who declared his state as the Kushan state and made Dalvarzintepa, now located in the Shurchi district of Surkhandarya region, the capital of this country. Under King Kudzula Kadfiz, the Kushans conquered much of present-day Afghanistan and Pakistan. During the reign of his successor, Vima Kadfiz, much of India was annexed by the Kushans. The heyday of the Kushan state dates back to the reign of Kanishka (ca. 78-123 AD). Researcher A. Biykuziev classified this as follows: “By 90 AD. The Kushan kingdom has finally lost its status as a semi-nomadic state and turned into a centralized empire. Tsar Kanishka I (78–123) was already the head of a multi-ethnic empire” (1, 43) at that time, the capital was moved from Bactria to Peshawar, and the country's borders extended to India and Hotan. In Central Asia, the borders of the Kushan state passed through the peaks of the Hisar mountain range in southern Uzbekistan. There, in the high mountain valleys (Darband), fortified frontier structures were erected, new cities were built, and trade relations were established with India, China, and the Roman Empire. During the excavations in Pompei, Kushan coins and bone objects were found by Kushan masters. Architecture was highly developed during the Kushan period. Much attention was paid to the construction of palaces and temples. In the palace of the Kushan rulers in Kholchayon, in the old Buddhist temples in Termez and Dalvarzin, artistic taste, skillfully designed wall drawings and sculptural specimens are well preserved. Archaeological excavations have revealed more than 120 towns and villages of the Kushan period in the Surkhandarya region. Ancient city excavations such as Qoratepa, Fayoztepa, Zormola, Ayritom and Dalvarzintepa in ancient Termez [11]

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Tourism is considered the future of our economy. At a time when tourism is receiving a lot of attention at the national level, it is important that we make long-term plans for what we need to do in this area. A vivid example of this is the words of President Sh. Mirziyoyev: “Tourists should travel and not wander in the police”. If we want to create jobs at the expense of tourism, we must create conditions, not conditions for tourists [12], we can cite the idea that.

Today Uzbekistan is in the center of attention of the world with its numerous historical and architectural monuments, unique climate and rapid development. Foreigners are interested not only in the beautiful cities of Uzbekistan, but also in the famous and well-known places of pilgrimage and archeological sites. Among these monuments are the ruins of Qoratepa, Fayoztepa, Zormola, Ayritom and Dalvarzintepa in Termez, the southern pearl of the Surkhandarya region, which dates back to the Kushan Empire. The discovery that Fayoztepa was one of the centers of ancient Buddhism has led to an increase in the influx of tourists from Japan, a predominantly Buddhist country.

For centuries, Uzbekistan has been on the Great Silk Road for trade, merchants and travelers, geographers and missionaries, invaders and conquerors. At the same time, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the most attractive tourist destinations for entrepreneurs, interested in culture, history, traditions and exotic countries. A lot of work is being done to develop archeological tourism. One of such actions is the promotion of the potential of archeological tourism in Uzbekistan, which was held in Turkey on April 24-27, 2019, and the participation of participants from Turkey and other Turkic countries in the development of the field of archeological tourism [13].

On August 24, 2020, at the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, an archaeological and tourism forum “Uzbekistan at the crossroads of civilizations” was held in Termez. The meeting was attended by Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Aziz Abdukhakimov, Director of the Middle East and Central Asia Program at Hoffstra University, Professor A. Naymark (New York, USA), Director of the Institute of Art History of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Pidayev, M. Albricht (Poland), Head of the Department of Ancient History and Oriental Studies, Jeshua University.

“Archaeological excavations in Surkhandarya continue to reveal new details of the history of the Central Asian region. One of the latest unique discoveries is the famous Oxus Alexandria, now located in the town of Kampirtepa. This truly sensational discovery elevates the ancient city to one of the most Hellenistic centers in the world. The Hellenistic Ax Alexandria, the towns of Fayoztepa and Qoratepa, the magnificent Termez Archaeological Museum, the Kushan Treasure - all these are the bright pages of our history, the unique artifacts that have survived to our days. Popularization of history is important

not only in science, but also in the development of tourism. By disseminating information about different historical periods, we can draw the attention of the general public to the monuments that have survived from the past,”said Aziz Abdukhakimov.

Within the framework of the forum there was a presentation of the video clip “Kushan’s Heritage”. After that, “The connection with the antique period as a factor of cultural development”, “The Hellenistic period: The meeting of East and West in the heart of Asia, “Kushan Empire: the greatness of ancient civilization” branch meetings were held. Well-known archaeologists and historians of the world took part in them [14].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Tourism” states that tourist resources are a combination of natural climatic, health-improving, historical, cultural, educational and social facilities of the region. In the Russian-language literature, tourist resources are understood as natural-climatic, socio-cultural, historical, architectural and archaeological, scientific and industrial, picturesque, religious and other objects that can satisfy human needs in the tourist process and purposes. Tourist resources are a national treasure, but the most important of them are international objects and monuments. Such a list is established annually by UNESCO. It is known that Uzbekistan is one of the countries rich in historical and cultural resources. It has been a long time since much of this precious heritage has become the property of humanity. International tourism centers should be further developed. All cultural monuments and natural sites are under state protection, and United Nations funds are allocated for the preservation and support of monuments of international importance. In Egypt, for example, Abu Simbal, which was flooded during the construction of the Aswan Dam (a site on the west bank of the Nile River, has two ancient Egyptian temples built on rock). They were built in the first half of the XIII century BC. It contains statues and reliefs. In front of the main temple are 4 huge statues of Ramses II sitting) 40 million rupees to preserve the temple and its facilities. U.S. dollars are allocated. This valuable object has been dismantled, moved to higher ground and renovated. Unfortunately, part of the unique historical structure has been submerged, and now tourists are exploring them by water transport. In the same way, we can look for ways to raise UN funds to preserve the Kushan treasure and show the world our masterpieces [15].

CONCLUSION

Archaeological sites are of great social, cultural and economic importance at the national and international levels. Archaeological sites are an integral part of regional history and heritage. In this regard, we must revive our history and develop the tourism industry at a high level to promote these places to the world. In order to study the spheres of the Kushan Empire on a larger scale, we need to consider the possibility of developing and implementing strategic programs for attracting more foreign investment and development and we need to build special tourist pavilions that can attract the attention of tourists and create conditions for every tourist to imagine themselves in that period. Only then will Uzbekistan's tourism revenues increase and the majority of the population will be employed.

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ASSESSMENT OF THE CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE MIDDLE EAR IN TYMPANOSCLEROSIS

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ABSTRACT: Tympanosclerosis is a chronic non-suppurative disease of the middle ear, a distinctive characteristic of which is the formation of specific sclerotic foci in the thickness of the mucous membrane of the middle ear and / or the tympanic membrane, which leads to damage to the sound-conducting apparatus and hearing loss. According to the literature, the prevalence of this pathology ranges from 3.3 to 33% among all patients with chronic otitis media, which allows us to speak of tympanosclerosis as a common disease.

KEYWORDS: воздушная проводимость, костно-воздушный интервал, цепь слуховых косточек, наружный слуховой проход.

INTRODUCTION: We observed 40 patients with a diagnosis of tympanosclerosis. All patients underwent anamnesis collection, complaints, clinical, laboratory, instrumental, otomicroscopic and audiological research methods.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS:

Refixation of the stirrup after its mobilization is the most common cause of unsatisfactory functional outcomes of tympanoplasty in patients with tympanosclerosis with fixation of the stirrup. Tympanoplasty, including mobilization of the stapes and ossiculoplasty with simultaneous prophylactic creation of a support for the prosthesis, the piston in the thickness of the non-tympanic membrane in the absence of a hammer handle and a long incus, allows to optimize the tactics of reoperation in case of re-fixation of the stapes.

Ossified foci of tympanosclerosis are bone sequestrs, and not fragments of "new" bone tissue formed as a result of connective tissue metaplasia.

Tympanosclerosis is a slowly progressive dystrophic disease of the middle ear, characterized by a lesion of the mucoperiost with malnutrition of the underlying bone up to the development of aseptic necrosis.

The functional results of tympanoplasty according to the developed method practically do not differ from the results of traditional variants with the use of prostheses, but the implementation of this variant of tympanoplasty in patients with an open form of tympanosclerosis with fixation of the stapes in the absence of an anvil and malleus makes it possible to carry out stapedotomy during reoperation using a piston prosthesis when the stapes are fixed. without additional surgical stage of neomalleus formation.

The lack of evidence of osteogenic cellular transformation and osteogenesis of the intercellular substance in the samples studied allows us to seriously doubt the validity of the assumption about the possibility of the formation of "new" bone tissue as a result of connective tissue metaplasia in tympanosclerosis. Ossified tympanosclerotic foci are nothing more than bone sequestration from dystrophically altered areas of the auditory ossicles or bony walls of the tympanic cavity.

Morphological changes in the incus in patients with tympanosclerosis, characterized by the destruction of bone tissue with a predominance of sclerotic changes in the absence of signs of exacerbation, indicate a slowly progressive dystrophic nature of the disease with low process activity.

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